

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

SERENA Deliverable D2.3.2

Cookbook to evaluate indicators of soil threats, soil-based ES and their associated bundles over scenarios of change

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Abstract

Soil's vulnerability to soil threats (STs) and its capacity to deliver soil based ecosystem services (SESs) depend on specific environmental conditions. Therefore, STs and SESs require to be assessed using explicit and appropriate methodologies. Indicators are suitable communications tools with stakeholders and the general public because they facilitate the simplification of complex human-environmental systems and provide aggregated information on certain phenomena at the spatial and temporal scale that they represent. Task 2.3 of the SERENA project was aimed at developing harmonised methodologies to evaluate bundles of soil threats (STs) and soil-based ecosystem services (SESs) at different levels. The Deliverable 2.3.1 developed the second step of the harmonization of STs and SESs indicators, whereas this deliverable developed the third step of the global tiered strategy for harmonisation and was mainly focused on the definition of methods for the harmonised assessment of indicators of STs and SESs at the member state (MS) level. The deliverable was focused on soil erosion (ST) and soil erosion control (SES), soil organic carbon (SOC) loss (ST), greenhouse gas (GHG) and climate regulation (SES), and soil sealing (ST) as well as a bundle of STs/SESs. Different cookbooks were developed to provide harmonized approaches/methods for assessing indicators for STs/SESs at national scale. The cookbooks for each indicator of ST/SES (including bundles of STs/SESs) reported in this deliverable were provide to Task 3.2 for their application at MS scale and subsequent validation of these applications by Task 1.3.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AFP	Air-Filled Porosity
CEC	Cation Exchange Capacity
DC	Degree of Compaction
EEA	European Environment Agency
EJP	European Joint Programme
ES(s)	Ecosystem service(s)
EU	European Union
JRC	Joint Research Center
MS	Member State
NEP	Net Ecosystem Productivity
NPP	Net Primary Production
NPPpot	Potential Net Primary Production
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OM	Organic matter
RE CARE	Preventing and Remediating degradation of soils in Europe through Land Care
RND	Relative Normalized Density
SERENA	Soil Ecosystem seRvices and soil threats modelling aNd mApping
SES(s)	Soil-based ecosystem service(s)
SIREN	Stocktaking for Agricultural Soil Quality and Ecosystem Services Indicators and their Reference Values
SOC	Soil organic Carbon
SS	Soil Stress

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ST(s)	Soil threat(s)
WLCC	Wheel Load Carrying Capacity
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

The common principles for soil protection throughout the EU are established in the Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection (EU 2006) according to which MS will be able to decide how to protect soils as well as possible and how to use soils sustainably. These principles find their accomplishment in a general approach aimed to make soil monitoring obligatory (European Commission, 2023). Since human life and ecosystems depend on soil, seven possible threats to soil were defined in the strategy (soil compaction, soil erosion, soil salinisation, soil organic matter decline, landslides, pollution and sealing). The last two threats (pollution and sealing) depend on external factors not related to specific soil conditions and therefore require a general or national protection strategy (European Commission, 2006). The Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection has been updated by the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2021a), which is aimed at exploiting the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate. The Soil Strategy for 2030 requires the establishment of a framework and concrete measures for the protection, restoration and sustainable use of soil that simultaneously mobilises the commitment of society, makes available the necessary financial resources, shared knowledge, sustainable practices and monitors the achievement of common goals. The EU vision for soil by 2050 (European Commission, 2021a) is aimed at achieving that all soil ecosystems are in a healthy condition and hence more resilient to global change and able to provide as many of soil-based ecosystem services (SESs) as possible. The EU vision for soil by 2050 is also related to the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2020) and to the Climate Adaption Strategy (European Commission, 2021b) and is aimed at contributing significantly to several objectives of the European Green Deal and Sustainable Development Goal 15.3 (United Nations, 2015).

In this context, the concept of ecosystem services has acquired a huge and growing attractiveness for environmental scientists, managers and decision makers (Müller et al., 2016); and has required both defining and measuring ecosystem services (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2016). In addition to defining what an ecosystem service is, it was necessary to create a conceptual framework that related the set of ecological structures and related processes and how they benefit people (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2011).

The soil's vulnerability to soil threats (STs) and capacity to deliver soil based ecosystem services (SESs) depend on specific environmental conditions, therefore both STs and SESs require to be assessed using explicit methodologies that are appropriate for these conditions. Indicators are suitable communications tools with stakeholders and the general public, as they facilitate the simplification of complex human-environmental systems and provide aggregated information on certain phenomena at the spatial and temporal scale that they represent (Müller et al., 2016; Stein et al., 2001). Therefore, indicators have become suitable tools for assessing STs and SESs at different scales of variation, both spatial and temporal. Although there is a rich literature on methodologies for assessing indicators of STs and SESs, there are still large discrepancies in the definitions of specific STs and ESs, in the indicators used to assess them, in the procedures for assessing such indicators, in the type and origin of the primary data used in these procedures and finally in the spatial (and temporal) extent and resolution at which the STs and SESs are provided (van Beek et al., 2010; Faber et al., 2022). This prevents a consistent assessment of vulnerabilities related to STs and SESs at the EU level. Achieving the objectives of the EU Soil Strategy, and all those related to it (e.g., policies, measure, etc.), requires

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that results of different methods and procedures of evaluation are comparable and consistent. An easy way forward would be a standardization of methods using identical assessment procedures for every ST/SES throughout the EU and thus the selection of a single assessment methodology for all MS (van Beek et al., 2010). That is often not possible because procedures should be suitable for the local context and, therefore, there is a need for a harmonisation procedure to ensure comparability and consistency of results from different methods (van Beek et al., 2010).

Task 2.3 of the SERENA project is thus aimed at developing harmonised methodologies to evaluate bundles of soil threats (STs) and soil-based ecosystem services (SESs) at different levels. For this purpose, a global strategy towards the harmonisation of the assessment of STs and SESs at the EU level was first developed in Deliverable 2.3.1 (Montagne et al., 2024). The strategy included four successive steps: i) the harmonisation of the conceptual framework for assessment and definitions; ii) the harmonisation of STs and SESs indicators; iii) the harmonisation of methods used in the assessment of STs and SESs indicators, and finally iv) the harmonisation of the input data necessary to use the selected methods. The first steps of the proposed approach were extensively addressed in Deliverables D2.1 (van den Elsen et al., 2022) and D2.2 (Foldal et al., 2024) and to which the readers are referred for further details.

The second step of the harmonization of STs and SESs indicators, developed in the Deliverable 2.3.1 (Montagne et al., 2024), is summarized briefly in Chapter 4.

This report develops the third step of the global strategy for harmonisation and is mainly focused on the definition of methods for the harmonised assessment of indicators of STs and SESs at the member state (MS) level. Methods to assess STs and SESs indicators are described in form of cookbooks in Chapter 5 for soil organic carbon loss, soil erosion, and soil sealing, and to some SESs, namely greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration, and erosion control.

2. Inputs and links from SERENA work packages (WP) and tasks (T), and other projects

2.1. Links between Task 2.3 and other Work Packages and tasks

Firstly, as a task of the SERENA WP2, the Task 2.3 is directly linked to the task T2.2 (Foldal and Oorts, 2023) in relation to the common harmonised definitions for the soil threats and ES between the 16 participating European member states in SERENA and the following prioritisation of soil threats and SES done by each member state and indirectly to the inputs of Task 2.1 (van den Elsen et al., 2022) for the concepts used in SERENA (soil quality, soil health, soil threats, soil functions, soil-based ES, bundles) with their associated definitions, and develop a framework linking these concepts' (Fig. D2.3.2.1).

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Figure D2.3.2.1: Links between WP2 tasks and other WP tasks

Task 2.3 is also linked to Task 3.1 and Task 5.1 that perform a comprehensive review on existing data (maps, databases, reports, etc.) on STs and SESs in each MS and at the EU level respectively, with the aim of providing a critical analysis of existing experiences at different levels (field/farm, local, regional, national and European).

In turn, Task 2.3 should provide input to Tasks 3.2, 3.3 and 5.1. In particular, Task 3.2 tested the indicators for assessing STs and SESs at the MS scale included in the cookbook of harmonised estimation methods produced by Task 2.3. The results of the application of the cookbooks in different MS is described in Deliverable 3.3 (Hessel, 2024). Similarly, Task 5.1 will have to test the same harmonised methods for assessing indicators of STs and SESs at the EU scale.

Task 2.3 is finally closely related to Task 3.3 and Task 5.2 to forecast the effect of change scenarios on the levels of STs and SESs. This will be done particularly for bundles of STs and SESs.

2.1.1. Conceptual framework and definitions: consequences for harmonisation

First of all, being based on the cascade model by Potschin and Haines-Young (2011), the SERENA conceptual framework (Fig. D2.3.2.2) recognised ESs as integral parts of the natural (eco)system. Within the natural system, ESs are distinguished from functions by their direct or indirect, total or partial contribution to human well-being (when combined with other inputs). SESs are finally defined as the subset of the ESs that are directly and quantifiably controlled by the soil physical, chemical or biological properties through the classical production chain: properties, processes, functions and ultimately services (Dominati et al., 2010). STs are in turn defined as the set of processes able to

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degrade the soil conditions, their functions and the delivery of (some of) the SESs. According to these definitions, indicators of services have to be clearly distinguished from indicators of soil condition and soil functions, whereas indicators of STs have to be distinguished from pressure or impacts indicators.

The SERENA framework also highlights the link between land use and soil management and the supply of the SESs, either through ameliorative management increasing soil quality or through unsustainable management leading to soil degradation. Indicators of STs and SESs are then expected to be responsive to changes in land use and land management. A practical way to ensure the sensitivity of ST and SES indicators to soil use and management is to select indicators that are not only based on inherent soil properties but also on manageable soil properties (Dominati et al., 2010).

Finally, bundles may concern SESs as commonly defined in most of the literature, STs, or the combination of the two and are defined as the STs and SESs that appear together in time or space.

Figure D2.3.2.2: The SERENA conceptual framework under development (23 August 2022 version)

2.1.2. Between interest and implementation at the EU level, the selection of a list of soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services for first implementation in T2.3

Four STs and three SESs have been selected for the development and testing of the indicator harmonisation procedure according to two complementary criteria. The first one referred to the high interest of SERENA’s partners for these STs and SESs, as indicated in the D2.2 deliverable (Foldal and

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Oorts, 2023). The second one was some input from T5.1 and T5.2 of previous literature review that had assessed these particular STs and SESs at EU level. The selected STs and SESs were:

- For STs: soil erosion; soil organic carbon loss; soil compaction; and soil sealing;
- For SESs: primary biomass production; erosion control; and greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration.

However, the procedure for selecting an indicator for harmonisation, developed and tested here for a subset of STs and SESs, could be extended to the whole set of STs and SESs of interest in SERENA using an approach similar to the one described in this deliverable. Besides the STs and SESs of the highest interest and assessed at least once at the EU level, threats like nutrient imbalance, soil acidification, salinization, soil contamination or loss of soil biodiversity as well as services like water provision and regulation could be considered in the future.

2.2. Links between T2.3 task and other projects

Task 2.3 is closely related to the EJP SOIL Internal Project SIREN that produced a synthesis of policy-relevant soil quality indicators with high potential for harmonised application in national and EU monitoring based on literature, international policy, international stakeholder opinions, wide application in national soil monitoring and EU projects. Moreover, in SIREN a comprehensive conceptual framework linking soil quality to SESs has been developed from the review of scientific literature by unifying various concepts associated with soil quality and SESs.

Other important links are found between Task 2.3 and the project Preventing and Remediating degradation of soils in Europe through Land Care (RECARE) (www.recare-hub.eu). This project was funded by the European Commission FP7 Programme, ENV.2013.6.2-4 'Sustainable land care in Europe'. The most relevant RECARE result for Task 2.3 is the framework developed in the Work Package 2 (Base for RECARE data collection and methods), which provides an overview of existing information on STs and soil degradation at the EU scale (Tesfai et al., 2015). The STs considered by RECARE were: (1) soil erosion by water, (2) decline of organic matter (OM) in peat, (3) decline of OM in mineral soils, (4) soil compaction, (5) soil sealing, (6) soil contamination, (7) soil salinization, (8) desertification, (9) flooding and landslides, and (10) decline in soil biodiversity. Each ST was defined, described, and related to the soil processes involved, the state of the soil degradation by each ST was provided together with drivers/pressures (including climate, human activities, policies) for their occurrence. In addition, key ST indicators and methods for their assessment were listed, along with the effects of each of them on other STs and soil functions.

3. A tiered approach for harmonisation

Developing an assessment of bundles of STs and SESs fully harmonised at the EU level was conceptualized in four successive steps, as described in Figure D2.3.2.3

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The first step is to harmonise the conceptual framework and associated definitions. Although the harmonisation of main concepts and specific definitions has long been recognised as a mandatory initial step for harmonisation (Boyd and Banzhaf, 2007; Nahlik et al., 2012), the EJP SOIL Internal Project Stocktaking for Agricultural Soil Quality and Ecosystem Services Indicators and their Reference Values (SIREN, <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/siren/>) still identified large differences in the definitions of the most commonly used terms (e.g., soil health, soil quality, etc.) and in the definition of individual STs and SES (Faber et al., 2022). In the SERENA project, the harmonisation of the conceptual framework and definitions of related concepts was achieved in task T2.1 (van den Elsen et al., 2022), while the harmonisation of the definition of the individual ST and SES was achieved in task T2.2 (Foldal et al., 2024).

The second step was to harmonise the indicators used to measure the levels of individual ST and SES, hereafter called STs or SESs indicators. Reflecting the diversity of STs and SESs definitions as well as the diversity of environmental, political and social conditions, or, more simply, the availability of primary data, a huge diversity of indicators is currently used to infer particular ST or SES across countries or, within countries, across regional and local studies (Faber et al., 2022). Such diversity considerably limits the comparability of assessments within or among countries. In that respect, harmonising indicators will increase the comparability of assessments. Leaving open the choice and the practical implementation of specific approaches to assess these “harmonised” indicators will allow each country to make the best use of the data and expertise at its disposal. It should be noted though that if the variables used to measure specific STs or SESs are harmonised, this does not imply that reference and target values are harmonised too. Apart from being impossible to harmonise due to the use of different exact methods, reference and target values should probably not be harmonised but used to reflect the diversity of climatic, soil or land use and management conditions among or within countries.

Figure D2.3.2.3: A tiered approach to harmonise the assessment of soil threats and soil-based ES at the EU Level

The third step was to harmonise the tools or methods used for the assessment of individual ST and SES indicators, for the mapping of these indicators as well as methods for the identification (and mapping) of bundles of STs and SESs. In this step, only the tools and models used are harmonised but not the

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input data used to run these tools and models that are still allowed to vary among or within countries. Such harmonisation of the methods is an important step towards the comparability of actual status of STs and SESs among countries. The main challenge is to find the right balance between complex but potentially accurate approaches and simpler but less accurate approaches (Bagstad et al., 2013).

The final step was to harmonise the input data used to run the tools and models harmonised in the previous step in terms of sampling, analytical methods and spatio-temporal resolution. It is highly unlikely that all countries change their own well-established programme of acquisition and monitoring of primary data needed to maintain long term monitoring of environmental conditions. The set of tools/models selected at the previous stage could, however, be run on datasets harmonised at European or global level, such as the dataset under preparation in Work Package 6 of EJP SOIL. The development of such a harmonised dataset goes largely beyond the objectives of the task T2.3. Such final step in harmonisation will insure the complete comparability of the status and trends of STs and SESs among countries.

Given that EU countries are moving at different speeds with respect to evaluation of ST/SES, and with different levels of detail, a fully harmonised methodology for the assessment of STs and SESs at the EU level will inevitably deviate from the most recent scientific advances. On short time scales, the comparison of the fully harmonised methodology with such up to date methodologies will be very helpful to develop comparative studies (Bagstad et al., 2013; Vorstius and Spray, 2015) and ultimately to indicate how the cookbook could be improved. On longer time scales, the preliminary harmonisation of indicators will pave the way for step-by-step refinement of tools, models and spatio-temporal resolutions as capacity is built in the different countries.

4. Towards indicator harmonisation: the selected indicators of ST/SES

The first step towards the harmonisation of the individual assessment and mapping of STs and SESs consisted in harmonising the indicators used in the individual assessment of ST and SES (Fig. D.2.3.1.3). The identification of potential indicators for STs and SESs was done in three successive steps. As a first step, only the indicators already used to map STs or SESs at EU level were considered. Indeed, by definition, these indicators met two important criteria for indicator selection (Rendon et al., 2022): they were quantifiable (i.e., they could be quantified from available existing data in Europe) and available [i.e., they were either spatially explicit or available at NUTS (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) (EU, 2020) 2 level maximum]. Assuming that these indicators also fulfilled criteria such as relevance (i.e., they adequately quantified the threat or service of interest according to its specific definition) or communicability (see Table D2.3.1.2 for the full list of criteria) and that the models currently used to quantify them at the EU level were relevant, the assessments at EU level of these STs or SESs could be considered as "ready-to-be-harmonised" data. The indicators used, at least once, for the assessment of the STs and SESs of interest in SERENA were reviewed and listed by T5.1 and T5.2 (Table D2.3.1.1).

While this first list contains a significant diversity of potential indicators for some STs (e.g., soil erosion) or SESs (e.g., biomass production or erosion control), only a few indicators could be identified for other STs (e.g., soil organic carbon loss or soil sealing) or SESs (e.g., the greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration). This list of indicators used for the assessment at EU level

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of STs and SESs was complemented in a second step with indicators used at national level by the different MS involved in the SERENA project. The indicators used at the national level in the different MS involved in the SERENA project have been stocktaken by T3.1 (Foldal et al., 2024; Michel, 2023). If none of the indicators currently used in the assessment of STs and SESs at the EU or MS levels were selected to be the “harmonised indicator” at the EU level, an in-depth literature review was carried out by T2.2 and T2.3 in order to complement the first two lists with indicators used at sub-national levels and/or outside MS involved in the SERENA project.

4.1. Development of a framework for indicators’ ranking

A template was developed to score and rank the indicators selected for each ST and SES according to multiple criteria (Table D2.3.1.2). The development of the template was based on the existing literature (OCDE, 2002; Feld et al., 2010; Layke et al., 2012; Muller and Burkhard, 2012; van Oudenhoven et al., 2012; Faber et al., 2013; Stone et al., 2016; van Oudenhoven et al., 2018; Thakur et al., 2022) in order to highlight the main criteria currently used by the scientific community to select and assess the suitability of indicators to provide information related to a given SES or ST. For instance, Layke et al., (2012) propose two main criteria to evaluate the adequacy of indicators: i) the availability of data that should fit multiple spatio-temporal scales, be accessible and normalized; ii) the ability of the indicator to convey information, which means that the indicator should be intuitive, sensitive and widely accepted. Other authors suggested the importance of the object represented by the indicator, which can for example refer to the supply of the service, its use, demand or interests by human societies (Geijzendorffer et al., 2017). Finally, van Oudenhoven et al. (2012, 2018) proposed exhaustive lists of multiple criteria, which also integrate the importance of stakeholder’s and user’s objectives, focusing on the flexibility and inclusivity of the selection process of the indicators.

A total of seven criteria divided in three main families were finally selected:

1. **Scientific soundness.** This family of criteria estimates the adequacy of the representation of the targeted object according to three complementary criteria: i) the scientific adequacy and suitability of the indicators in fitting the purpose and object of the assessment (fitness-to-purpose, 1); ii) the possibility and ease of spatial and temporal comparison (interpretability, 2); and iii) the sensitivity to changes in external conditions (sensitivity, 3);
2. **Availability of data.** It estimates the feasibility of using a particular indicator according to two criteria: i) the availability and measurability of the indicator (measurability, 4); and ii) the existence of past applications of the indicator, especially at the EU level (scalability, 5);
3. **Ability to convey information.** It estimates the suitability of the indicator to the objectives that stakeholders expect from its application. This is assessed through two criteria: i) understandability of the indicator by various stakeholders (intuitivity, 6); and ii) their implementation in current environmental policies (policy-relevance, 7).

Scoring levels ranging from 0 (i.e., lowest score) to 12 (i.e., highest score) were finally defined for each of these indicators. The 0 to 12 scale was chosen to give the same weight to all the criteria classified on 3, 4, 5 or 6 different levels. The indicator scores were finally represented graphically through radar charts to better identify the “weak” and “strong” features of each indicator. Indicators were selected on the basis of a balance between scientific soundness, ability to convey information and a rough

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estimation of data availability (through scales for past implementations). No precise consideration on the availability and reliability of data and methodologies was made. For this reason, that 'Ideal' indicators were selected for each ST or SES, but when lack of data or other requirements were not met, alternative 'pragmatic' indicator were selected. All details on selection of indicators of STs and SESs can be found in the Deliverable 2.3.1 (Montagne et al., 2024).

5. Cookbooks for assessing the selected indicators of soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services

The aim of cookbook was to describe methodology to evaluate the selected indicators in such a way that each member state (MS) was able to apply the methodology. Some requirements or assumptions were established:

- ✓ Selection of at least one method per indicator (e.g. RUSLE for soil erosion). Perhaps 2, if possible.
- ✓ Assuming mapping at national scale
- ✓ Methods should be feasible for MS (data, software, knowledge)
- ✓ Standard format 'recipe', different methods ST/SES
- ✓ Threshold/reference values to evaluate.

The development of cookbooks for each indicator of ST/SES (including bundles of STs/SESs) was only one part of a broader activity that would involve several WPs of SERENA for the subsequent application of the cookbooks at MS scale and the validation of the results of this application. Therefore, intertask working groups were set up to have all the necessary expertise and carry out all the necessary steps related to the different stages in which the activities were organized (Table D.2.3.2.1). More details can be found in Deliverable 3.3 (Hessel, 2024).

Table D.2.3.2.1: Stages in development and application of cookbooks (from Hessel et al., 2024).

Stage	Tasks	Result
1. Critical analysis of methodologies (links to T3.1)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Review available MS info in SERENA (e.g. T3.1) 2. Review literature and other sources 	Selection of methodology to be included in cookbook
2. Develop cookbook (links to T2.3)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Write cookbook for selected methodology 2. Revise cookbook based on feedback MS/region test 	Final version of cookbook, which could be applied by all MS
3. Test and apply cookbook (links to T3.2)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Test draft cookbook 2. Provide comments to development group 3. Apply final version cookbook 	Map that can be compared to current results (from T3.1)

Among the STs/SESs, only some of them were selected for developing the cookbooks. The selection was based on their importance within SERENA, the interest of MS in specific ST/SES, the possibility to evaluate specific ST/SES, and the availability of expertise and time of the researchers involved in SERENA and in particular in the individual intertask working groups. Therefore, the following STs/SESs were selected for developing the cookbooks:

1. Soil erosion (ST) and soil erosion control (SES)
2. SOC loss (ST)
3. Greenhouse gas (GHG) and climate regulation (SES)
4. Soil sealing (ST)

To these was added a cookbook of bundles of STs/SESs. Bundles are the result of combining and synthesizing different STs and SESs that are in some way related and that share some of the information provided by the individual STs/SESs indicators. The aim of the bundle is the effectiveness of reporting the status of some STs/SESs in a single indicator.

The different cookbooks were aimed to providing a harmonized approach/method for assessing an indicator for each ST/SES at national scale. However, a certain amount of autonomy of choice was left to each individual MS in relation to the availability of data and expertise within it.

5.1. Soil organic carbon loss (ST)

5.1.1. Selected indicators

Soil organic carbon stock (SOCS) loss (Mg C ha^{-1}) was selected as **ideal indicator** of soil organic carbon loss. However, it is a dynamic estimation of the change in SOC stocks, which would require the availability of national SOC data sets covering at least two periods of time separated by a certain

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number of years. Moreover, assessing SOCS, as shown in the equation that follows, would require other data:

$$SOCS (Mg C ha^{-1}) = \frac{SOC \times D \times BD \times \left(1 - \frac{SCF}{100}\right)}{10}$$

where:

SOC (g C kg⁻¹ soil) which is numerically the same of mg g⁻¹), soil organic carbon

D (cm), soil sample thickness

BD (g cm⁻³), soil bulk density

SCF (% of soil sample volume), soil coarse fragments content.

For these reasons, lacking at least two datasets of SOC and BD and SCF, the solution was to select a **pragmatic indicator** as soil organic carbon (SOC) concentration (often referred to as content) (g C kg⁻¹ soil or %1 was selected).

5.1.2. Selected methodology:

The assessment of the SOC loss indicator at the EU Member State level is an extension of SOC concentrations measured at selected sampling points to unsampled locations in the Member State in question. Such an extension requires a spatial analysis of the available SOC data and its prediction to the unsampled locations and its subsequent mapping. The spatial prediction of SOC at unsampled locations might be made using different methods depending on the available data. Among these is the well-known Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) (McBratney et al., 2003; Lagacherie et al., 2007), which uses more densely measured auxiliary variables/maps (secondary data, ancillary maps, environmental covariates) to improve soil mapping.

The specific methods to be used within the DSM depend on the availability of data. Useful references can be:

- ✓ Chapter 5 'Harmonized procedures for creation of soil maps'. WP6 EJP Soil Deliverable 6.1 'Report on harmonized procedures for creation of databases and maps' (D6.1).
- ✓ SOC mapping Cookbook (<https://www.fao.org/documents/card/en/c/I8895EN/> or WsG folder)

The application of DSM approaches can be facilitated thanks to the DSM workflow developed within EJP Soil WP6 and located in the ISRIC data hub (Genova et al., 2024). Information on how to install and run the DSM workflow can be found at <https://shiny.wur.nl/content/71ff48b3-6e26-4b6b-8d07-ec9a05c64cc8/>. The DSM workflow allows to access a large number of covariate data and scripts to apply different approaches that include algorithms ranging from geostatistical methods to machine learning.

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5.1.3. Scope/output

The indicator in itself does not allow a real assessment of the threat SOC loss. However, mapping SOC at EU member state scale can provide an overview of the SOC situation and identify areas with different SOC content for the promotion and implementation of sustainable agricultural soil management. In addition, maps of individual EU member countries can be the basis for comparison with SOC maps obtained from simulated scenarios of land-use change, climate change or both.

5.1.4. Data and harmonization

Data from SOC national data set, if available, otherwise EU data. To obtain EU SOC point data (LUCAS 2018), one needs to make a request at the following link: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/resource-type/soil-point-data>.

In the case of ESDAC data, there is no need for harmonisation. On the contrary, in the case of national datasets, it will be a matter of checking the quality of the data and their consistency (depth, method of SOC measurement, time, etc.) on a MS-by-MS basis.

5.1.5. Software

Any GIS software package including the required spatial analysis modules.
Any software or R/Python packages for spatial interpolation
DSM workflow (Genova et al., 2024).

5.1.6. Application

Application of the different approaches possible is not straightforward and based on the specific method different levels of expertise could be requested.

Detailed instructions on how to apply the method can be found in the publications that are mentioned above and are therefore not repeated here.

In case where it is not possible to apply the DSM method described in section 5.1.2 a map of SOC content can be made by spatial interpolation of measured SOC values. This could be done with spatial stratification (e.g. per land use or soil type), but in its simplest form also without stratification. In that case, the resulting map will only provide a first indication, but in the absence of other data this can still be a valuable first step.

5.1.7. Interpretation

As mentioned above, maps of SOC content do not allow analysis of SOC loss but can be a first step in understanding SOC distribution at MS level, which can provide information relevant for the preservation of SOC stocks.

How much can be concluded from the maps also depends on the methodology used for interpolation. The more elaborate methods, such as DSM, provide more information on the reasons why SOC content vary is space. Simple methods like kriging provide more of a first indication.

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Interpretation should also be done in the geographical context. It is for example well known that SOC content tends to be lower in Mediterranean areas than in Boreal regions. Therefore, it is not possible to provide threshold/reference values that are of use throughout the EU.

5.1.8. Further reading

De Rosa, D., Ballabio, C., Lugato, E., Fasiolo, M., Jones, A., & Panagos, P. (2023). Soil organic carbon stocks in European croplands and grasslands: How much have we lost in the past decade? *Global Change Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16992>

Genova, G., Poggio, L., Kempen, B., & Colman, B. (2024). DSM Workflow Seedling. *ISRIC - World Soil Information*. <https://doi.org/10.17027/ISRIC-FSX2-2691>

Lagacherie, P. (2008). Digital Soil Mapping: A State of the Art. In A. and M.-S. M. de L. Hartemink Alfred E. and McBratney (Ed.), *Digital Soil Mapping with Limited Data* (pp. 3–14). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8592-5_1

McBratney, A. B., Mendonça Santos, M. L., & Minasny, B. (2003). On digital soil mapping. *Geoderma*, 117(1), 3–52. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(03\)00223-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(03)00223-4)

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5.2. Soil erosion (ST) and soil erosion control (SES)

5.2.1. Selected indicators:

The amount of soil loss per year by water erosion, sheet and rill, was a pertinent indicator of erosion threat as it allows estimating actual risk (and potential either) of the ST given the current conditions. **Total soil loss** [t (or Mg) ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹] was selected as **ideal indicator** of soil erosion. However, data availability and difficulties in estimating all types of erosion, suggested the selection of a **pragmatic indicator** as **soil loss by water erosion** [t (or Mg) ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹].

Several indicators had already been applied to assess **soil erosion control** (SES) at the EU level but none of them represented the fraction of the reduction in the loss of soil materials involved in mitigating or preventing potential damages to human use of the environment or human health and safety. **Total amount of soil not eroded** was selected as **ideal indicator** of soil erosion control, but for the same considerations about soil erosion and for the lack of assessment at different periods of time (at least two), soil loss by water erosion was selected as **pragmatic indicator of soil erosion control** [t (or Mg) ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹].

5.2.2. Selected methodology

The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) was selected.

Elaborated by: Rudi Hessel, João Coblinski, Gabriele Buttafuoco, Sylwia Pindral, Blandine Lemerrier, Annamária Laborczy.

5.2.3. Scope/output

The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) was selected because it is conceptually simple and possible to use by different MS. RUSLE was designed to calculate the long-term average soil loss from sheet and rill erosion under specific conditions (Renard et al., 1997; Wischmeier and Smith, 1978). In the RUSLE approach, other forms of water erosion (e.g., gully erosion) or deposition are not considered. The soil loss for a given location is calculated as the product of six factors (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978):

$$A = R \times K \times LS \times C \times P \quad (1)$$

where A (Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) is the annual average soil loss, R (MJ mm ha⁻¹ h⁻¹ yr⁻¹) is the rainfall-runoff erosivity factor, K (Mg ha h ha⁻¹ MJ⁻¹ mm⁻¹) is the soil erodibility factor, LS (dimensionless) is the slope length and slope steepness factor, C (dimensionless, ranges between 0 and 1) is the cover-management factor and P (dimensionless, ranges between 0 and 1) is the support practices factor. Different examples of RUSLE application at EU scale are available (Bosco et al., 2015; Panagos et al., 2020, 2015e).

Equation 1 can be used for both the ST Soil Erosion and the SES Soil Erosion control. The C-factor (cover-management factor) is used to estimate both the ST and the SES. To estimate soil erosion (ST) the C-factor is set to 1, while for soil erosion control (SES) it is given a value based on land use, crop

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type and management. The difference in soil erosion is then taken to be the erosion that is prevented by the presence of vegetation.

5.2.4.Data and harmonization

For a RUSLE application at national scale maps of R, K, LS, C and P factors are needed. Different methods exist to calculate these factors. An extremely critical issue is to ensure that all factors are calculated from data associated with a similar support size. The complete specification of the term support includes the geometrical shape, size, and spatial orientation of the measurement volume. The support can be as small as a point or as large as the entire pixel (e.g., remote sensing images or available maps of RUSLE factors). In geostatistics it is possible to solve the problem of change of support by resorting to block cokriging, but there are also other possible approaches. Whatever method is used, a change of support size is necessary to make the different R-factors compatible. In the application section one method (or possible alternative for lack of data or other) for each factor is provided. To use the selected methods, the following data are needed:

Data	RUSLE factor
Rainfall intensity data	R
Soil textural particle-size fractions (sand, silt, clay) and organic carbon (SOC)	K
Digital elevation model	LS
Land use map	C
Cover crop map	C
Crop management map (tillage, residues, cover)	C
Landscape Management map (contouring, stone walls, grass margins)	P

It should be noted that because it was developed in the USA, RUSLE results were not originally expressed in the International System of Units (SI). In SERENA applications, the units of the International System were always used.

5.2.5.Software

Any GIS software package.
Any software or R/Python packages for spatial interpolation

5.2.6.Application

Application of the RUSLE equation in GIS is straightforward as it only requires multiplication of the different factors. However, calculating the individual factors is more complex. One method for each factor is described below.

5.2.6.1 R-factor (rainfall-runoff erosivity factor):

The R-factor quantifies the erosive power of rainfall, which is one of the most direct impacts that climate change can have on soil erosion amount. The intensity of the rain plays a special role in its erosive power.

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The calculation of the R-factor was originally described in Wischmeier and Smith (1978). The R-factor is the product of kinetic energy of a rainfall event (E) and its maximum 30-min intensity (I_{30}). (Panagos et al., 2015a) described its calculation in metric units (SI) according to (Brown and Foster, 1987):

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{mj} (EI_{30})_k \quad (2)$$

where R=average annual rainfall erosivity ($\text{MJ mm ha}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$), n is the number of years covered by the data records, m_j is the number of erosive events of a given year j , and EI_{30} (energy times intensity) is the rainfall erosivity index of a single event k . The erosivity EI_{30} ($\text{MJ mm ha}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) of a single event is defined as:

$$EI_{30} = \left(\sum_{r=1}^0 e_r v_r \right) \times I_{30} \quad (3)$$

where e_r is the unit rainfall energy ($\text{MJ ha}^{-1} \text{mm}^{-1}$) and v_r is the rainfall volume (mm) during a time r^{th} period of rainfall divided in k -parts. I_{30} is the maximum 30-min rainfall intensity (mm h^{-1}) of the whole event. The calculation of the unit rainfall energy (e_r) for each time interval is based on rainfall intensity i_r (mm h^{-1}) in the same time interval as follows (Brown and Foster, 1987):

$$e_r = 0.29 \times [1 - 0.72 \times \exp(-0.05 i_r)] I_{30} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the mean annual erosivity sums the erosive events during a given period and it is divided by the number of years.

The R-factor calculation requires the identification of erosive rainfall events (m_j) for each station. The criteria for the identification of an erosive event are given by (Renard et al., 1997):

1. the cumulative rainfall of an event should be greater than 12.7mm, or
2. the event has at least one peak that is greater than 6.35mm in 15 min and
3. a rainfall-period of less than 1.27mm in 6 h is used to divide a longer storm period into two storms.

In many erosion studies, simplified multiplications (Arnoldus, 1980) have been used or in other cases, because of the lack of stations with sub-hourly data for long periods and measured intensity, the development of simple empirical equations correlating R-factor with daily/monthly/annual rainfall data have been developed (Diodato and Aronica, 2014).

Alternatively, geostatistical algorithms for spatial interpolations contributed to regional, national, and continental erosivity datasets from high temporal resolution data (hourly, sub-hourly) and for long periods (Diodato et al., 2013, 2014; Panagos et al., 2015a).

In the case of lack of data, a solution is offered by the work done by a group of scientists, working with R-factor data all over the world, who have collected data on rainfall erosivity from 3,625 meteorological stations in 63 countries and established the Global Rainfall Erosivity Database

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(GloReDa, <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/global-rainfall-erosivity>) to develop a global erosivity map (Panagos et al., 2017). The data have been produced in 2013-2017 and can be requested free of charge from <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/global-rainfall-erosivity>.

5.2.6.2 K-factor (soil erodibility factor)

The K-factor quantifies the erodibility of soil or susceptibility of soil to erosion. It represents the rate of soil loss per unit of rainfall erosivity index as measured on a unit plot (approx. 22.13 m in length) of uniform slope (9%) continuously in clean-tilled fallow (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978). Direct measurements of the K-factor at the EU member state scale are not available, so it is necessary to use one of several available equations, the choice of which, apart from the accuracy and quality of the K-factor values obtained, depends on the availability of the input data required by each of these equations.

Excluding nomograph calculations and equations requiring data on soil water infiltration, soil permeability and total water capacity, two equations were selected that only require data on the three soil particle size fractions and the concentration of organic carbon.

One of these is included in the EPIC model (Sharpley and Williams, 1990), and K-factor is calculated as follows:

$$K = \left\{ 0.2 + 0.3 \times \exp \left[-0.0256 \times Sand \left(1 - \frac{Silt}{100} \right) \right] \right\} \times \left(\frac{Silt}{Clay + Silt} \right)^{0.3} \times \left[1 - \frac{0.25 \times SOC}{SOC + \exp(3.72 - 2.95 \times SOC)} \right] \times \left(1 - \frac{0.7 SN_1}{SN_1 + \exp(-5.51 + 22.9 \times SN_1)} \right) \times 0.1318 \quad (5)$$

in which

$$SN_1 = 1 - \frac{Sand}{100}$$

Where sand, silt, clay, and soil organic carbon (SOC) are their respective concentrations in percentage (%). The results (K) are expressed in SI units as $Mg \ h \ MJ^{-1} \ mm^{-1}$.

A second equation based on a global dataset compiled from published studies was proposed by (Torri et al., 1997). The soil erodibility factor K is calculated using a regression equation having as inputs soil textural size fractions and organic matter (OM) concentration:

$$K = 0.0293 (0.65 - D_G + 0.24 D_G^2) \exp \left\{ -0.0021 \frac{OM}{C} - 0.00037 \left(\frac{OM}{C} \right)^2 - 4.02 C + 1.72 C^2 \right\} \quad (6)$$

where:

OM = organic matter content expressed as a percentage;

C = clay content expressed as a fraction;

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D_G = decimal logarithm of the geometric mean of soil particle size and is calculated using the following equation:

$$D_G = \sum f_i \log_{10}(\sqrt{d_i d_{i-1}}) \quad (7)$$

where:

d_i = maximum diameter of i^{th} particle size class (mm)

d_{i-1} = minimum diameter of i^{th} class (mm)

f_i = fraction of primary particles (clay, silt, sand) with sizes within d_i and d_{i-1} as defined by (Shirazi et al., 1988)(Shirazi et al., 1988)(Shirazi et al., 1988).

The data to be used are those from national databases and in case there is no national database, data provided by the Joint Research Centre in Ispra (Italy) will be used.

5.2.6.3 LS-factor (slope length and slope steepness factor)

LS-factor (slope length and slope steepness factor)

Tips and tricks: The calculation of LS factor is complex, but an LS map can be downloaded from: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu> (ESDAC). For countries the spatial resolution is 25 m, while for the whole EU it is 100 m.

The recommended method is described in (Panagos et al., 2015b).

For S the calculation is as follows:

$S = 10.8 \times \sin \Theta + 0.03$, where slope gradient < 0.09 deg

$S = 16.8 \times \sin \Theta - 0.5$, where slope gradient ≥ 0.09 deg

where Θ is the gradient of slope in degrees.

For calculating L, Panagos et al. (2015b) used the equation of Demet and Govers (1996) who used the concept of unit-contributing area for two-dimensional terrain:

$$L_{i,j} = \frac{(A_{i,j-i_n} + D^2)^{m+1} - A_{i,j-i_n}^{m+1}}{D^{m+2} \times X_{i,j}^m \times 22.13^m} \quad (8)$$

where $A_{i,j-i_n}$ is the contributing area at the inlet of grid cell (i,j) measured in m^2 . D is the grid cell size (meters), $X_{i,j} = \sin a_{i,j} + \cos a_{i,j}$, the $a_{i,j}$ is the aspect direction of the grid cell (i,j) .

m is related to the ratio β of the rill to interrill erosion:

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$$m = \frac{\beta}{\beta + 1} \quad \text{where} \quad \beta = \frac{\frac{\sin \theta}{0.0896}}{\left[0.56 + 3 \times (\sin \theta)^{0.8}\right]} \quad (9)$$

It is to note that possible maximum slope is 50% (26.6 degrees). Next, a method is required to combine S and L terms to obtain the LS-factor. Panagos et al. (2015b) estimated the LS-factor by using one of the hydrology modules available in SAGA GIS (the LS-factor field base), which incorporates the multiple flow algorithm (Pilesjö et al. 2014). Moreover, SAGA GIS carries out computations much more quickly than other commercial GIS software and calculates flow accumulation directly from the DEMs.

5.2.6.4 C-factor (cover-management factor)

The calculation of the C-factor is based on the method described by (Panagos et al., 2015c). In that study, a C-factor has been calculated for the arable lands of each NUTS2 region as follows:

$$C_{arable} = C_{crop} \times C_{management} \quad (10)$$

where C_{crop} is the C-factor based on the crop composition of an agricultural area, and $C_{management}$ quantifies the influence of management practices (reduced tillage, cover crop and crop residues) on soil erosion reduction. Values of C_{crop} for 17 crops are reported in Table D.2.3.2.2.

Table D.2.3.2.2: Ccrop values for 17 crops (Panagos et al., 2015c).

n	Crop type	Share (%) of the total arable land (EU-28)	C-factor
1	Common wheat and spelt	28.5	0.20
2	Durum wheat	3.2	0.20
3	Rye	3.0	0.20
4	Barley	14.8	0.21
5	Grain maize – corn	12.9	0.38
6	Rice	0.6	0.15
7	Dried pulses (legumes) and protein crop	1.9	0.32
8	Potatoes	2.4	0.34
9	Sugar beet	3.1	0.34
10	Oilseeds	5.8	0.28
11	Rape and turnip rape	8.1	0.30
12	Sunflower seed	4.8	0.32
13	Linseed	0.1	0.25
14	Soya	0.5	0.28
15	Cotton seed	0.4	0.50
16	Tobacco	0.1	0.49
17	Fallow land	9.8	0.50

$$C_{management} = C_{tillage} \times C_{residues} \times C_{cover} \quad (11)$$

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$C_{tillage} = 1$ for conventional tillage; 0.35 for conservation/ridge tillage; 0.25 for no till practices.

$C_{residues} = (0.88 \times F_{residues}) + (1 - F_{residues})$, where $F_{residues}$ is the fraction of arable land treated with plant residues [0...1].

$C_{cover} = (0.80 \times F_{crop-cover}) + (1 - F_{crop-cover})$ where $F_{crop-cover}$ is the fraction of arable land to which cover crops are applied during winter or spring [0, ..., 1].

Information on C-factor for other land uses is given in Tables D.2.3.2.3 and D.2.3.2.4.

Table D.2.3.2.3: Mean C-factor for different land uses, based on remote sensing (Panagos et al., 2015c).

Group	CLC class	Description	% of the area	C-factor values
Permanent crops	221	Vineyards	1.3%	0.3527
	222	Fruit trees & berry plantations	0.9%	0.2188
	223	Olive groves	1.4%	0.2273
Pastures	231	Pastures	12.9%	0.0903
Heterogeneous agricultural areas	241	Annual crops associated with permanent crops	0.3%	0.2323
	242	Complex cultivation patterns	8.2%	0.1384
	243	Land principally used for agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation	6.7%	0.1232
	244	Agro-forestry areas	1.2%	0.0881
Forests	311	Broad-leaved forest	14.7%	0.0013
	312	Coniferous forest	22.1%	0.0011
	313	Mixed forest	10.3%	0.0011
	321	Natural grasslands	3.9%	0.0435
Scrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations	322	Moors and heathland	2.8%	0.0420
	323	Sclerophyllous vegetation	3.2%	0.0623
	324	Transitional woodland-shrub	8.7%	0.0219
	333	Sparsely vegetated areas	1.3%	0.2652
Open spaces with little or no vegetation	334	Burnt areas	0.04%	0.3427
	TOTAL (Non-arable)		100%	0.0539

Table D.2.3.3.4: C-factors per land use per country in Europe (Panagos et al., 2015c)

Cover Type (class)	Vineyards	Olives	Pastures	Complex cultivation	Agriculture & natural areas	Forests	Grasslands	Transitional woodland & Shrub	Sparse vegetation
Country	221	223	231	242	243	31X	321	324	333
AT	0.3403		0.0853	0.1300	0.1211	0.0012	0.0345	0.0215	0.2308
BE			0.0893	0.1286	0.1153	0.0011	0.0372	0.0216	
BG	0.3750		0.1185	0.1517	0.1449	0.0016	0.0498	0.0302	0.2889
CY		0.2524	0.1256	0.1659	0.1595	0.0019	0.0639	0.0359	0.3780
CZ	0.3546		0.0927	0.1506	0.1253	0.0014	0.0391	0.0235	0.2865
DE	0.3111		0.0920	0.1282	0.1219	0.0012	0.0421	0.0235	0.2810
DK			0.0905	0.1250	0.1152	0.0012	0.0424	0.0216	0.2648
EE			0.0829	0.1171	0.0997	0.0009	0.0342	0.0171	0.2794
ES	0.3963	0.2413	0.0901	0.1585	0.1457	0.0015	0.0516	0.0296	0.3517
FI			0.0971	0.1102	0.0981	0.0009	0.0273	0.0161	0.2052
FR	0.3363	0.2145	0.0906	0.1302	0.1195	0.0012	0.0403	0.0229	0.2581
GR	0.3269	0.2094	0.1132	0.1476	0.1307	0.0014	0.0522	0.0260	0.3062
HR	0.3254	0.1981	0.0975	0.1461	0.1193	0.0011	0.0440	0.0228	0.2752
HU	0.3605		0.1167	0.1583	0.1491	0.0017	0.0564	0.0306	0.3564
IE			0.0770	0.1087	0.0902	0.0010	0.0294	0.0165	0.2171
IT	0.3454	0.2163	0.0988	0.1478	0.1245	0.0013	0.0416	0.0242	0.2509
LT			0.0873	0.1224	0.1021	0.0011	0.0389	0.0190	0.2822
LU	0.2905		0.0907	0.1254	0.1107	0.0011		0.0231	
LV			0.0819	0.1169	0.0944	0.0010	0.0331	0.0171	0.2671
MT					0.1483				
NL			0.0900	0.1317	0.1126	0.0013	0.0489	0.0251	
PL			0.0933	0.1358	0.1214	0.0012	0.0432	0.0231	0.3115
PT	0.3313	0.2216	0.1030	0.1432	0.1342	0.0015	0.0491	0.0270	0.2858
RO	0.3460		0.1026	0.1398	0.1313	0.0013	0.0419	0.0242	0.2449
SE			0.0833	0.1082	0.0947	0.0009	0.0317	0.0162	0.2301
SI	0.2993		0.0965	0.1359	0.1185	0.0013	0.0447	0.0244	0.2864
SK	0.3433		0.0922	0.1465	0.1212	0.0013	0.0395	0.0228	0.2254
UK			0.0867	0.1201	0.1068	0.0011	0.0319	0.0183	0.1825
EU-28	0.3527	0.2273	0.0903	0.1384	0.1232	0.0012	0.0435	0.0219	0.2652

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The same land-cover class may have different C-factors due to variations in vegetation density.

F_{cover} is a vegetation layer available in the Copernicus programme and normalized in the range [0–1], which describes the % of soil covered by any type of vegetation. It is used to calculate:

$$C_{NonArable} = Min(C_{landuse}) \times Range(C_{landuse}) \times (1 - F_{cover}) \quad (12)$$

Based on this approach, the C-factor reaches its maximum value when the F_{cover} is equal to 0 (no vegetation protection, and high risk of erosion) and its minimum value when the F_{cover} is equal to 1 (soil is fully covered by vegetation).

5.2.6.5 P-factor (support practices factor)

Map available at: [Support Practices factor \(P-factor\) for the EU - ESDAC - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://eodac.europa.eu) (ESDAC) (Resolution: 1 km)

Methodology is described in (Panagos et al., 2015d). At the European level, the effect of support practices (compulsory for farmers to receive incentives under the CAP-GAEC) on soil loss were assessed by P-factor estimation taking into account a) contour farming b) maintenance of stone walls and c) grass margins.

The P-factor in the RUSLE2015 model is estimated as the product of 3 sub-factors:

$$P = P_c \times P_{sw} \times P_{gm} \quad (13)$$

where P_c is the contouring sub-factor for a given slope of a field, and P_{sw} is the stone walls sedimentation sub-factor (known as terrace sub-factor), and P_{gm} is the grass margins sub-factor (known as strip cropping sub-factor and includes effects of grass buffer strips). P_c values as a function of slope are provided in Table D.2.3.2.5.

Table D.2.3.2.5: P_c values as function of slope (Panagos et al., 2015d).

Slope (%)	Support practice factor for contouring, P_c
9–12	0.6
13–16	0.7
17–20	0.8
21–25	0.9
>25	0.95

For P_{sw} , Panagos et al (2015e) arrived at an estimate of 0.32-0.71, depending on stone wall density.

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For P_{gm} , Panagos et al (2015e) assumed that grass margins trap on average half of the sediments compared to those trapped by stone walls. Thus, depending on the density of grass margins, the P_{gm} -factor will vary from 0.66 to 0.85. Table D.2.3.2.6 gives values of P_{sw} and P_{gm} .

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Table D.2.3.2.6: Density of stone walls and grass margins along a transect (LUCAS database) and assigned P-factor (P_{sw} is stone walls sub-factor, P_{gm} is grass margins sub-factor) values for Europe (Panagos et al., 2015a).

No of features (stone walls or grass margins)	% of total stone walls observations	P_{sw}	% of total grass margins observations	P_{gm}
0	95.08%	1	72.99%	1
1	2.51%	0.707	11.36%	0.853
2	1.10%	0.577	9.73%	0.789
3	0.53%	0.500	3.06%	0.750
4	0.32%	0.448	1.70%	0.724
5	0.15%	0.408	0.60%	0.704
6	0.10%	0.378	0.30%	0.689
7	0.06%	0.354	0.12%	0.677
8	0.05%	0.334	0.07%	0.667
>8	0.09%	0.317	0.07%	0.660
Total	100.0%		100.0%	

An Appendix is included with some details and scripts.

5.2.7. Interpretation

Panagos et al. (2020) used $2 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ as threshold for sustainable soil loss, and $11 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ as threshold for severe erosion. Baritz (EEA, 2023) considered $2 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ a suitable threshold for shallow soils and $4 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for deep soils. As also discussed in Baritz (EEA, 2023), other authors consider $5\text{-}10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ as moderate erosion, and $>10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ as severe erosion. Based on this, we propose the following classes for the legend of the soil erosion map:

- 0- $2 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: no soil erosion (0)
- 2- $5 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: slight soil erosion (1)
- 5- $10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: moderate soil erosion (2)
- $> 10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: severe soil erosion (3)

For the soil erosion control map, the difference between the erosion map with C-factor = 1 (soil erosion without vegetation) and C-factor according to land use, crop type and management (soil erosion with vegetation) is calculated:

Soil erosion control = Soil erosion without vegetation – soil erosion with vegetation

For the soil erosion control map, two types of legend are possible, both with their own advantages and disadvantages:

- Absolute: The legend could, like for soil erosion, be given in $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ of soil erosion that is avoided. Class boundaries might need to be different and should have the possibility for negative change (though this would not be expected). This provides information on the true reduction, but less on the change in severity or the exceedance of thresholds.
- Classes: The legend could be expressed in change of erosion class, e.g. -1 means erosion class has decreased 1 class (e.g. from >10 to $5\text{-}10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). As not all erosion classes have the same range, and the range for the higher classes is largest, not all changes may be visible in the resulting map.

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Legends for both methods are best defined once the range of results is available. For starting, possible classes are suggested in Table D.2.3.2.7.

Table D.2.3.2.7: Classes for soil erosion control map. Note that negative values indicate that erosion has increased due to vegetation; this is unlikely but model-wise it is possible.

Absolute (Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)		Classes	
values	legend	values	legend
< -5	Large increase	-3	Large increase
-5 - -1	Small increase	-2	Moderate increase
-1 - 1	No change	-1	Small increase
1 - 5	Small decrease	0	No change
> 5	Large decrease	1	Small decrease
		2	Moderate decrease
		3	Large decrease

As mentioned before, the rates simulated by RUSLE refer to rill and interrill erosion and do not include the effects of gully erosion, streambank erosion or deposition. As such, the results of RUSLE cannot be compared to sediment yield data from catchments, unless assumptions are made for these other processes (such as on the sediment delivery ratio).

We would also like to point out that soil erosion control as used in the cookbook cannot be used directly to evaluate the effect of measures in comparison to arable fields without measures. This because the calculation compares a situation without vegetation (C=1) to a situation with vegetation (C smaller than 1). Arable fields generally do not have zero vegetation (except perhaps at some specific moments). Thus, arable fields already have a C-factor below 1; measures that improve vegetation cover would result in a further reduction of the C-factor.

In the absence of validation data, the best way to evaluate the result is to compare the input maps with the output map to see whether results are in line with expectations (e.g., higher erosion for steeper slope, higher erodibility, higher erosivity, poorer cover, etc.), in combination with expert opinion on predicted absolute values and predicted erosion patterns.

5.2.8. Further reading

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5.3. Soil sealing

5.3.1. Selected indicators

Degree of soil sealing (ha ha^{-1}). Proportion of an area that is covered by artificial, (semi-)impermeable materials.

5.3.2. Selected methodology

Level 1: semi-automatic classification process of multitemporal images and photointerpretation; Level 2 machine learning model

Elaborated by: Daniela Smiraglia, Kasper Cockx, Sabina Asins-Velis, Luca Congedo, Cecilie Foldal, Ines Marinosci, Katrien Oorts, Nicola Riitano, Paolo De Fioravante, Francesca Assennato, Michele Munafò

5.3.3. Scope/output

Soil sealing is “the permanent covering of soils by buildings, constructions and layers of completely or partly impermeable artificial material (asphalt, concrete, etc.). It is the most intense form of land take and is a hardly reversible process. Soil sealing is causing loss of essential soil ecosystem functions” (Huber et al., 2008; Prokop et al., 2011; Stolte et al., 2015; Tobias et al., 2018).

Artificial materials and covers of the following land use classes are taken into consideration: buildings, paved roads, train railroads, airports, ports, impervious non-built areas and sports fields, paved greenhouses, and landfill sites.

The degree of soil sealing is the proportion of an area (ha ha^{-1}) that is covered by artificial, (semi-)impermeable materials. To assess the soil threat (ST) of soil sealing, it is helpful to compare the degree of soil sealing through time ($\text{ha ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$).

To map and assess the degree of soil sealing at the national level, a hierarchical approach is proposed:

- Level 1: semi-automatic classification process of multitemporal satellite images. The methodology uses vegetation and backscatter indices calculated over time series of images, and decision rules. The semi-automatic classification supports the subsequent photointerpretation phase based on national orthophotos and other free VHR satellite images (e.g. through Google Earth or Bing services). The final maps are the product of a binary classification (sealed/not-sealed) having 10 m spatial resolution;
- Level 2: a case study for Flanders (Belgium) as an example of a more detailed mapping methodology is proposed for supporting users in generating more detailed mapping products, if needed.

5.3.4. Data and harmonization

Level 1

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- It is recommended to use the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Layer Imperviousness 2018 as reference data to start the procedure, as this layer has a 10 m resolution and is available for EU countries.

Go to

<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-imperviousness/imperviousness-density-2018#download>

and select your “Area of interest” at 10 m resolution, then press “Add to cart” button and follow the instruction for downloading.

Unzip the files and open the files in a GIS software, like QGIS.

- Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 tiles of the period to monitor (follow the instructions in chapter 4);
- Administrative boundaries shapefile;
- VHR images and orthophotos to support photointerpretation;
- grid (2x2 km) shapefile to support the photointerpretation

Level 2

Annual soil sealing maps of Flanders (Belgium)

In order to monitor the evolution of sealed surfaces, and thus the effectiveness of sealing-related policy measures, in Flanders (Belgium), a method was developed for automatically generating annual and spatially detailed (1 m resolution) soil sealing maps for this region. These maps combine “known” sealing from administrative databases (buildings and transport infrastructure) with modelled sealing based on artificial intelligence.

Large-scale Reference Database

The “administratively known” soil sealing was derived from the [Large-scale Reference Database](#) (LRD, *Grootschalig Referentiebestand*), the digital topographic reference map for Flanders. Different (parts of) vector layers of the LRD were selected for delineating buildings, roads, railways and water (see Cockx et al. (2022) for more details). For each year for which an annual soil sealing map was prepared, the LRD state on 31 December of the year under consideration was used.

Aerial imagery

Flanders’ administrative databases do not (adequately) cover parking lots, private driveways and garden terraces, which are a substantial part of the sealed area in Flanders. Hence, a machine learning model was built for deriving these types of sealing from aerial imagery. For this purpose, the publicly available [medium-scale annual winter aerial images](#) between 2012 and 2020 of Flanders, available in 418 map sheets with a 25 cm resolution, were used.

5.3.5. Software

Level 1

- A Google Earth Engine account is required to process the data, as the procedure is written in Python. It can be requested at the following link: <https://code.earthengine.google.com/register>. It is available free of charge for non-commercial and research projects (<https://earthengine.google.com/noncommercial>).

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After the registration and authentication, open the following link, which is a Google Colab Notebook:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1Ychh0u2zd0A8DHvjvkoLGF1IZVCPnlAo?usp=sharing>

It contains detailed instructions and the Python code required for the monitoring of soil sealing as described in Luti et al. (2021).

- Any GIS software package. If QGIS is used as suggested later, you need to install the following plugins:
 - Semi-Automatic Classification: The plugin offers three important functions to support photointerpretation: the display of multi-temporal images in Google Earth, the display of multi-temporal Sentinel-2 images and the use of keyboard shortcuts for faster switching on and off of layers in QGIS. In addition, you can visualize the GE images by linking the view of the QGIS project to the Google Earth software;
 - QuickMapServices: the plugin allows you to view images from Google, Bing and other sources in QGIS. The basemaps are useful as a support for the photo interpreter, but cannot be used for photointerpretation, since the date of acquisition of the different portions of the basemap is not known;
 - Topology Checker: the plugin is useful for identifying topological errors in geometries, such as wrong intersections, overlaps and invalid geometries. The plugin is necessary for verifying the final photointerpretation.

Level 2

For Flanders, a machine learning model was built using the semantic segmentation of the U-Net model (Ronneberger et al., 2015). The actual training of the model was done with TensorFlow (Abadi et al., 2015) in Python. All other calculations and processes were written and executed in R or Python.

5.3.6. Application

Level 1

Study area and monitoring period definition

First, we define a study area. The monitoring process implemented in this cookbook works on the geometric boundaries defined by a Sentinel-2 tile that must be specified.

It is required to define the monitoring period in order to detect changes between two years:

- Year 1, named "previous year"
- Year 2, named "reference year"

For example, Year 1 can be 2018 and Year 2 can be 2019, so that the changes between these years are monitored. In particular, the methodology considers the changes that occurred between March of the previous year and March of the reference year because of reporting requirements.

In addition, a shifted period starting from June to December is considered, to also detect the changes that occurred after the start of the reference year.

Enter the reference year. The monitoring dates will be automatically defined according to the reference year.

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Sentinel-2 methodology for change detection related to vegetation removal

The processing of Sentinel-2 images involves the calculation of the NDVI indices in the reference year and previous year, with the aim to detect a difference in values that may be related to vegetation removal because of soil sealing.

The first step is the selection of Sentinel-2 images for the three periods (reference year, previous year and shift period).

In Google Earth Engine, the groups of images such as Sentinel-2 time series are called collections. Selecting the images by a date range produces a new collection.

Sentinel-2 pre-processing

Pre-processing involves the masking of clouds identified in the image, which must be removed from the image to avoid outliers in the calculation of vegetation indices. The masking function will be executed on every image in the collection. In Google Earth Engine, a function can be applied to all the images by using the method *map*.

Sentinel-2 NDVI calculation

The NDVI is calculated for each image in the three collections, producing 3 new collections of NDVI rasters.

As an example, we can display the NDVI raster calculated for the first image in the collection (Fig. D2.3.2.4) of the reference year (with dark green colors for low NDVI values and light green for high NDVI values). We can see the clouds masked as NoData (transparent) in the raster.

Figure D2.3.2.4: NDVI raster for the first image in the collection

Calculation of maximum NDVI in the period range

As described in Luti et al. (2021), we calculate the maximum NDVI value per pixel for each period.

In Google Earth Engine, the method *reduce* applied to the function *ee.Reducer.max()* allows for calculating the pixel based maximum of the collection (i.e. the three periods).

Calculation of the NDVI difference and the change mask

Now we can calculate the NDVI difference between the previous year and reference year, as well as the NDVI difference between the previous year and the shift period.

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We can display the difference between the previous year and reference year in the map (Fig. D2.3.2.5), with green color representing NDVI values increasing between the previous and reference year, and red colors representing NDVI values decreasing between the previous and reference year.

Figure D2.3.2.5: NDVI difference between the previous year and reference year in the map.

Calculate the Sentinel-2 change map

The calculated maximum NDVI and NDVI difference between the previous year and reference year is then used to calculate the mask of changes with a conditional statement:

where

NDVI difference > 0.2

and

maximum NDVI for reference year ≤ 0.3

Therefore, pixels where the NDVI difference is higher than 0.2 and the maximum NDVI for the reference year is lower or equal to 0.3 are considered.

The same calculations are performed between the previous year and the shift period.

We can display the mask of possible changes related to the removal of vegetation (Fig. D2.3.2.6). The possible changes are displayed in red and represent pixels where the NDVI decreased between the previous year and reference year. This condition can frequently happen in the case of crop fields, causing false positives.

The Sentinel-1 processing (described in the following paragraph) aims to reduce these false positives.

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Figure D2.3.2.6: Mask of possible changes related to the removal of vegetation

Sentinel-1 methodology for change detection related to buildings and infrastructures

The Sentinel-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) data are used to detect possible changes, related to buildings or infrastructures, that increase the backscatter values. The Sentinel-1 polarization VV (vertical transmit/vertical receive) is used for mapping possible changes.

In addition, a soil cover mask is created to reduce the false positives of the Sentinel-2 change map. The Sentinel-1 polarization VH (vertical transmit/horizontal receive) is used for detecting these surfaces. First, Sentinel-1 images intersecting the Sentinel-2 tile are selected. The ascending and descending orbits are processed separately to avoid backscatter differences influenced by the geometry of the observation.

Sentinel-1 pre-processing

In the Sentinel-1 pre-processing phases, pixel values lower than -30 dB were considered outliers and therefore removed from the images.

Calculate a mask to reduce false change detection

Sentinel-1 backscatter values are related to surface characteristics such as roughness. Therefore, it is possible to map pixels having flat surfaces such as bare soil, which are not related to soil sealing, to reduce false positives in the Sentinel-2 change map.

This process involves calculation of the number of observations where the pixel backscatter value ≤ -20 (i.e. flat surfaces) for the reference year and previous year. A pixel is masked as 'flat surface' if this condition occurs for more than 30% of the valid observations for both the reference and previous years.

We can display the Sentinel-1 flat mask in green colour (Fig. D2.3.2.7), which represents mainly crop fields and vegetated areas.

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Figure D2.3.2.7: Sentinel-1 flat mask in green colour

Sentinel-1 change detection

Change detection using Sentinel-1 involves the calculation of several statistics such as the median of backscatter values (VV polarization) of the previous year and reference year, calculated separately for ascending and descending orbits.

Then, the following conditional statement is evaluated separately for ascending and descending orbits:

where

median of reference year - median of previous year ≥ 0.1

and

median of reference year < -9

and

NDVI of reference year < 0.5

The above condition also takes into account the NDVI for excluding vegetated areas from the possible changes. Therefore, the mask of possible soil sealing is calculated where both ascending and descending masks are verified.

Mask of possible soil sealing

The mask of possible soil sealing is the result of the overlay between the masks obtained from Sentinel-2 (related to vegetation removal) and Sentinel-1 (related to building and infrastructures).

The result is a raster having the following values:

- 1) Possible changes identified by both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 methodologies (very probable changes)
- 2) Possible changes identified by Sentinel-1 methodology
- 3) Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology
- 4) Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology with shift period (less probable)

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We can display the possible changes with the following colors (Fig. D2.3.2.8):

- blue: Possible changes identified by both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 methodologies (very probable changes)
- red: Possible changes identified by Sentinel-1 methodology
- orange: Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology
- yellow: Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology with shift period (less probable)

False positives can occur, in particular on crop fields.

Figure D2.3.2.8: Mask of possible soil sealing changes

Save the mask to Google Drive

We can save the output to Google Drive, which therefore can be downloaded for the next steps of photointerpretation. The raster is saved in a directory named 'land consumption mask' in the Google Drive main path.

The process can take a few minutes. The progress can be monitored at <https://code.earthengine.google.com/tasks>.

Photointerpretation of orthophotos and GE images

The photointerpretation and manual editing (drawing of polygons) is carried out using a GIS software (e.g. QGIS).

The suggested classification nomenclature follows the Eagle nomenclature for LCC Land Cover Component slightly modified (https://land.copernicus.eu/en/eagle?tab=document_archive). The hierarchical scheme is based on three levels (Table D.2.3.2.8) and the user can choose which legend level to adopt. The third level defines different kinds of permanent and reversible soil sealing. It is appropriate when very high-resolution images are available. The first and second level are used in other cases where the image spatial resolution is not adequate or if the user chooses a less detailed level.

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Table D.2.3.2.8: Legend of soil sealing classification

1 Artificial Surfaces	
11 Sealed Artificial Surfaces	
111)	Buildings
112)	Transport infrastructure (paved roads)
113)	Rail networks
114)	Airport installations (including their associated access infrastructures)
115)	Sea port installations (including their associated access infrastructures)
116)	Other sealed areas without buildings (squares, parking lots, sports fields, concrete or asphalt surfaces, etc.)
117)	Permanent paved greenhouses
118)	Dump sites
12 Non-Sealed Artificial Surfaces	
121)	Unpaved roads
122)	Construction site and other beaten earth lands (squares, parking lots, sports fields, permanent material storage areas, etc.)
123)	Extractive sites that are not renaturalized
124)	Quarries in groundwater
125)	Solar panels (ground-mounted)
126)	Other artificial coverage not connected to agricultural activities (if removed, the initial condition of soil is restored)
2 Other Surfaces (Biotic/Vegetation, Water, Natural Material)	

The photointerpretation must be carried out at a scale at least between 1:2,000 and 1:4,000, increasing the zoom level during editing where necessary.

After starting QGIS, you need to configure your workspace by installing and activating some important plugins:

- Semi-Automatic Classification: lets you visualize the GE images by linking the view of the QGIS project to the Google Earth software.
- QuickMapServices: lets you visualize Google, Bing and other QGIS source images.
- Topology Checker: lets you look over your vector files and check the topology with several topology rules.

To facilitate the photointerpretation phase, the following input data are needed:

- administrative boundaries shapefile;
- WMS services relating to Sentinel-2 data, VHR images and orthophotos to support photointerpretation;
- the soil sealing raster of the previous period (e.g. HRL Imperviousness 2018);
- the raster file of the mask;
- grid (2x2 km) shapefile (to support the editing) to mark the photointerpreted squares (Fig. D2.3.2.9). In order to check the area of interest in a systematic, complete and organised manner, it is useful to use a grid shapefile. With a monitor of at least 20" it is advisable to use a 2x2 km grid.

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In the grid attributes table, you need to create a field ("integer" type and 1 character long) to be filled in as you proceed with the inspection of the grid check as done. After having checked the square and after having identified and reported any errors or changes in the area, select the square and mark the corresponding field in the attributes table with the code 1. In this way, the checked area will be covered, and you will move on to the next square (Fig. D2.3.2.9);

Figure D2.3.2.9: Grid shapefile to mark the photointerpreted squares

- empty shapefile in which to add the photointerpreted polygons. The editing of the vector polygons is done on a single shapefile, containing a field for the year to be monitored (i.e. the reference year) and in which to insert the class code of identified polygons.

Then you can start with the editing tool and proceed with drawing the polygons and subsequently filling in the corresponding row in the attribute table with the classes from Table D.2.3.2.8.

Here some examples of photointerpretation (Fig. D.2.3.2.10 and Fig. D.2.3.2.11):

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Figure D.2.3.2.10: Basemap of the previous year (a) and the reference year (b). Black pixels = soil sealing map of the previous year, yellow pixels = mask of possible changes, purple line = photointerpreted polygon.

Figure D.2.3.2.11: Basemap of the previous year (a), the reference year (b), mask of possible changes (c), mask of possible changes and photointerpretation (d). Black pixels = soil sealing map of the previous year, yellow pixels = mask of possible changes, purple line = photointerpreted polygon.

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!!!! When comparing the mask with a high resolution image, the raster may not perfectly cover the edges of a paved area or building. This may depend on a shift between the image and the raster or on the rasterization process and the resolution of the mask file raster. In this case, it is not an omission error (Fig. Figure D.2.3.2.12).

Figure D.2.3.2.12: Example of an omission error (left). The yellow polygons (right) are not omissions.

!!!! Tunnels and bridges (over water bodies or natural soil) are not to be considered soil sealing and if reported in the mask, must be corrected.

!!!! Low density photovoltaics.

Many ground-mounted photovoltaic fields have a spacing between the rows that can sometimes be greater than the size of the panels themselves. In this case, it is not possible to map the site with a single polygon (class 125), due to the considerable presence of not-sealed area. It is recommended to measure the distance between the panels and the size of the panels themselves:

- If the space between the panels is smaller than the size of the panels themselves, the area can be mapped with a single polygon (class 125);
- If the space between the panels is greater than the size of the panels themselves and the size of the row is thought to be close to 5 meters (i.e. a size that is assumed to be able to cover half the pixel), polygons on each row can be drawn.

!!!! Final check of the file for topological errors.

At the end of the photointerpretation process, the data are converted into raster format (10 m spatial resolution) by attributing the class to each pixel based on the prevalent coverage within that pixel.

The final step concerns the combination of the raster file of the previous year and the raster file of changes to obtain the updated Soil Sealing Map.

In QGIS, use the Raster Calculator tool. The statement can be written as follows:

```
if ("Previous_year" <> 0, "Previous year", "Change")
```


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Accuracy assessment

The accuracy assessment of the final soil sealing raster is carried out based on the Olofsson methodology (Olofsson et al., 2014). This approach is widely used in literature and involves the identification of a sample of points through stratified random sampling, its photointerpretation using very high-resolution satellite data and the extraction of a confusion matrix.

The sample size (n) is calculated using the equation reported by Olofsson et al. (2014):

$$n = \frac{(\sum W_i S_i)^2}{[S(\hat{O})]^2} \quad (1)$$

where:

W_i = area proportion of each class i derived from the map of interest;

S_i = standard deviation of stratum i , $S_i = \sqrt{U_i(1 - U_i)}$;

U_i = user accuracy of class i ;

$S(\hat{O})$ = target standard error.

The W_i for each class is the ratio between the area of the class i and the total area (W) of the map and $\sum W_i = 1$.

The total number of the considered classes (c) depends on the classification level adopted for the mapping. For the first classification level mapping activity, $c = 2$ (sealed and unsealed land), while the number of classes increases if a higher level of detail is considered. The 'unsealed land' class must be included among the classes to be validated.

The S_i influences the sample size, and its value is related to U_i . A conservative scenario can be assumed, considering $U_i = 0.6$ for all classes; higher initial values of U_i lead to a reduction in the sample size.

An $S(\hat{O})$ value of 0.01 was assumed, as suggested by Olofsson et al. (2014), corresponding to a confidence interval of 1%.

The points are then allocated among each of the land cover classes through a stratified sampling. The number of points attributed to each class is assumed to be equal to the average between the equal and area proportional distribution:

$$n_i = \frac{\left(\frac{n}{c} + n \cdot W_i\right)}{2} \quad (2)$$

where:

W_i = area proportion of each class i derived from the map of interest ($\sum W_i = 1$);

n = sample size;

c = total number of classes;

n_i = number of points attributed to each class.

Points must be photointerpreted with very high-resolution images relating to the reference period of the classification (ground truth). The photointerpretation followed a pixel-based approach, assigning to each point the class on which it exactly falls.

After photointerpretation, two values will be associated with each point:

- the value at the point derived from the soil sealing map;
- the ground truth value attributed during the photointerpretation phase.

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Starting from the above values, it is possible to extract a confusion matrix, in which the rows correspond to the classified data classes (the soil sealing map to be validated) and the columns to the reference data classes (the ground truth).

All elements on the diagonal represent correctly classified points, while elements outside the diagonal are classification errors:

- Omission errors (O.E.), i.e. what part of a certain class has not been mapped. It is associated with producer accuracy (P.A., the relationship between the points of the class i that are correctly classified by the reference data and the total points mapped in the class by the reference data) and is calculated based on the columns; (3)
- Commission errors (C.E.), i.e. what part has been incorrectly attributed to a given class. It is related to user accuracy (U.A, the relationship between the points of the class i that are correctly classified by the reference data and the total points mapped in the class by the ground truth data) and is calculated based on the rows. (4)

In detail:

$$\text{Omission error} = 1 - P.A. \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Commission error} = 1 - U.A. \quad (4)$$

Accuracy assessment can be carried out according to two main practical approaches:

- Calculating the sample size and allocating the points on the classes using a spreadsheet and creating the points in the ESRI ArcGIS Pro GIS environment using the “create accuracy assessment points” command and generating the confusion matrix using the “compute confusion matrix” command;
- Conducting the entire procedure using the Semi-Automatic Classification Plugin for QGIS according to the procedure described in <https://fromgistors.blogspot.com/2019/09/Accuracy-Assessment-of-Land-Cover-Classification.html>.

Elaboration of soil sealing indicator (%)

The percentage of soil sealing (p) is calculated using the equation:

$$p = A_{\text{tot}}/A_s * 100$$

Where A_{tot} is the study area’s total area and A_s is the sealed area.

Level 2

Automatic generation of annual soil sealing maps for Flanders (Belgium)

To derive soil sealing in Flanders for each year, a hierarchical decision chain was set up for assigning each pixel to ‘sealed’ or ‘unsealed’ (**Error! Reference source not found.3**). First, information was collected from Flanders’ Large-scale Reference Database (LRD) and processed as the “administratively known” soil sealing for every year. In the next step, soil sealing was modelled using a machine learning model. Finally, the information from the previous steps was combined to produce an annual soil sealing map.

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Figure D.2.3.2.13: Overview of the sequential steps for compiling Flanders' annual soil sealing map. The thick arrows indicate the sequence of the decision chain for assigning a pixel to 'sealed' or 'unsealed'.

Processing of administrative soil sealing

Much of Flanders' soil sealing is covered by the LRD with high accuracy and at a high update frequency. It includes buildings, roads and railways, of which we are certain they seal the soil. Conversely, data from the LRD on water also provide information on what's certainly unsealed. The water and building layers from the LRD could be used directly. In contrast, roads and railways required additional processing to arrive at a usable layer. The finally obtained water, building, road and railway layers were converted to 1 m grid cells. These administratively known sealed and unsealed layers were given priority in the decision chain over the modelled soil sealing (**Error! Reference source not found.3**). Pixels covered by the administrative soil sealing were assigned their value based on that layer. Information from the modelled soil sealing was ignored in this process.

The **water** (Wtz) layer of the LRD was used to consider water courses and water surfaces as 'unsealed'. It was at the very top of the hierarchy for assigning a value to the annual soil sealing map's pixels.

For **buildings**, the Gbg, Gba ('afdak', 'uitbreiding', 'verdieping'), Knw ('cabine', 'schoorsteen', 'watertoren', 'silo', 'opslagtank', 'chemische installatie', 'overbrugging') and Trn ('verhard') layers from the LRD were used. Since the water layer takes precedence over all other layers, bridges over water were classified as 'unsealed'. This is in line with the definition of soil sealing, which requires a soil to be disturbed in order to be considered 'sealed'. The building layer took precedence over all underlying layers in the decision chain.

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The **road** (Wbn) polygons from the LRD often contain unsealed parts of e.g. motorways and roundabouts. As no polygon dataset of the purely sealed parts of roads existed at the time of the study, an algorithm was developed for deriving them (see Cockx et al. (2022: 8-9)).

As with the road layer, the **railroad** (Sbn) layer of the LRD includes unsealed parts. Similar to the road algorithm mentioned above, additional layers were therefore used for excluding these unsealed zones (see Cockx et al. (2022: 10)).

Modelling of soil sealing

Even though the LRD layers in the previous step already capture a large part of Flanders' soil sealing, a significant proportion in the form of e.g. car parks, private driveways and garden terraces is not (adequately) included in administrative databases. In order to account for this "remaining" soil sealing in Flanders, a machine learning model was developed. Specifically, semantic segmentation was chosen based on the U-Net model (Ronneberger et al., 2015). First, training data were created for teaching the model to detect soil sealing. Then, a modelled soil sealing map was created based on the model results. Finally, a continuity correction was also performed for ensuring a temporally consistent result. First, the **training** was conducted by manually labelling soil sealing on parts of the available aerial images for Flanders between 2012 and 2020. For this purpose, areas of 1,024 x 768 pixels were randomly cut from the orthophotos. An assessor then labelled the sealed soil (ground truth) in these areas on a tablet using specifically developed software (Fig. D.2.3.2.14). A total of 1,007 images of 4.92 ha each were labelled, corresponding to a total labelled area of 4,950 ha. After some initial tests, additional labelled material was selectively added for those instances where the model performed less accurately.

Figure D.2.3.2.14: Example of the labelling procedure: (a) image to be labelled, (b) display during labelling, (c) labelling result.

70% of the labelled images were assigned to the training set. Based on this, the model was trained to detect soil sealing on already known as well as new orthophotos. The remaining 30% served as a test set to validate the model's results.

The training data and corresponding labelling results were cut into smaller pieces for smoother processing by the model. To maximize the training data's value, six partially overlapping sub-areas of 512 x 512 pixels were derived from each original image of 1,024 x 768 pixels. For this purpose, the

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clipping window was shifted 256 pixels each time horizontally or vertically. Finally, all clipped images were also rotated 90°, 180° and 270° to obtain four times more material: 16,896 clipped images in the training set and 7,272 in the test set. The actual training of the model was done with TensorFlow (Abadi et al., 2015) in Python. Since no substantial improvement in accuracy was observed after 10 epochs – corresponding to submitting all images from the training set to the model once – training was stopped there.

A **modelled soil sealing map** was created for each year from 2012 to 2021 based on predictions by the trained model. Each 32,000 x 20,000 pixel map sheet was split into 512 x 512 pixel sub-areas (see above) for optimal performance. However, unwanted patterns may appear when merging model results due to inaccuracies in predictions at the images' edges. Therefore, the predictions were repeated on an offset version of the map sheet based on a horizontal and vertical shift of 256 pixels. This yielded a total of 5,040 512 x 512 pixel images per map sheet (2,520 without and 2,520 with offset). For each pixel, the average of the prediction with and without offset was calculated for a more reliable result with fewer artefacts. The obtained probabilistic map was then converted to a binary modelled soil sealing map. For this purpose, pixels with values below 50% were classified as 'unsealed' and those with values of at least 50% as 'sealed'. This binary map was converted to 1 m resolution for faster processing in the following steps.

A separate procedure was followed for military domains and nuclear sites. Since aerial images from 2016 onwards were blurred in these areas, all corresponding pixels in the modelled soil sealing map were considered 'unsealed'. Given that information on water, buildings, roads and railways (taken from the LRD database) is prioritized in the decision chain, and other soil sealing in these zones is limited, this produces a useful final result for these areas.

The method proposed resulted in modelled soil sealing maps for a series of consecutive years, so that each pixel's evolution over time could be analyzed. This showed that two changes in a pixel's soil sealing over two years (i.e. 'sealed' → 'unsealed' → 'sealed' and 'unsealed' → 'sealed' → 'unsealed') were almost always due to inaccuracies in the modelled soil sealing map. Therefore, a **continuity correction** was implemented for eliminating these discrepancies. Specifically, the binary assignment ('sealed'/'unsealed') for each pixel based on the modelled soil sealing map was considered for the year under consideration, the year before and the year after (**Error! Reference source not found.**9). For the previous year, the corrected label was used to reduce the probability of inaccuracies multiplying over time. If the label for the previous and the following year was the same, but differed for the year under consideration, that pixel was corrected. In all other cases, the original label was retained.

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Table D.2.3.2.9: Continuity correction of the pixels of the modelled soil sealing map.

<u>Corrected</u> label previous year	Original label year under consideration	Original label next year	<u>Corrected</u> label year under consideration
unsealed	<i>sealed</i>	sealed	remains sealed
sealed	<i>unsealed</i>	unsealed	remains unsealed
unsealed	<i>sealed</i>	unsealed	turns to unsealed
sealed	<i>unsealed</i>	sealed	turns to sealed

Compiling the annual soil sealing maps and assessing their accuracy

In the final step, the administrative and modelled soil sealing were compiled to an annual 1 m soil sealing map (Fig. D.2.3.2.15). The administrative soil sealing took precedence over the modelled information in assigning ‘sealed’ or ‘unsealed’. The obtained annual soil sealing map’s accuracy was determined using the same test set as for the validation of the machine learning model. However, the images from 2012 were first removed from this test set, because no annual soil sealing map could be prepared for that year due to the absence of LRD information. The selectively added labelled data for improving the model were also excluded because they were not sampled randomly. The remaining images were then manually checked for accuracy. If the assessor had labelled too much or too little soil sealing, this image was not used. Images showing trees completely covering roads were also not considered. Indeed, assessors had been instructed not to label these covered roads as ‘sealed’, since the model would not learn correctly from them. However, these roads do appear in the annual soil sealing map based on the road algorithm.

Finally, 159 labelled images remained, representing 782 ha for the years between 2013 and 2020. Based on this test set, the annual soil sealing map obtains an accuracy of 97.8%. This value is probably an overestimate, as the labelled data may contain small errors. The largest differences compared to the ground truth are situated at the edges of soil sealing, e.g. a road that is labelled just slightly narrower or wider than what eventually shows up on the annual soil sealing map.

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Figure D.2.3.2.15: Extract of the annual soil sealing map of Flanders of 2021 for the city of Mechelen.

5.3.7. Interpretation

In contrast to other soil indicators, baselines and thresholds for soil sealing are not soil science based, but rather policy based (e.g. in relation to the 'no net land take' target, EU 2013). Only a few European countries have set baselines and target values for soil sealing and land take, in most cases less strict than the EU target of 'no net land take by 2050'. Some EU member states voluntarily have set intermediary targets on net land take reduction by 2030. So far, only Flanders (Belgium), Luxembourg and Switzerland have set targets in line with the EU objective (EEA, 2023) (Table D.2.3.2.10).

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Table D.2.3.2.10: Current targets and baselines for soil sealing/land take in selected European countries (source: EEA 2023 modified)

Target	Indicator	Source
Achieve no net land take by 2050	Land take (km ²) per 3-year period	EU Roadmap to a resource efficient Europe (a)
To decrease land take gradually: 2016: baseline of 6 ha/day 2025: interim target of 3 ha/day 2040: final target of 0 ha/day ('land take neutral') To stabilise soil sealing in zones dominated by land take by 2050 compared to 2015 To reduce soil sealing by 20% in open space zoning by 2050 compared to 2015	Average annual land take measured in hectares per day Annual sealed surfaces measured in hectares and in percentage of the total area	Flanders (Belgium) Strategic vision of the Spatial Policy Plan of Flanders (b)
To reduce annual land take to 2.5 ha/day by 2030 and to compensate unavoidable soil sealing	Average annual land take measured in hectares per day	Austria Austrian government programme 2020-2024 (c)
To reduce land take for settlements and traffic routes to less than 30 ha/day by 2030 (at present 52 ha/day as a 4-year average from 2016 to 2019)	Average annual land take measured in hectares per day	Germany German sustainability strategy 2016 (d)
To reduce land consumption from 1.3 ha/day (average 2000-2006) to 1 ha/day by 2020 and 0 ha/day by 2050	Average annual land take measured in hectares per day	Luxembourg (e)
To halve land take at the expense of agricultural land until 2020 and reduce urban sprawl	Average annual land take measured in thousand hectares per year in metropolitan areas	France (f)
To stop net land (soil) take ('use') by 2050	Not yet defined	Switzerland (g)

Notes:

(a) EC, 2011, Communication from the Commission 'Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe' (COM(2011) 571 final of 20 September 2011).p. 15, milestone 4.6).

(b) *Strategic vision of the spatial policy plan of Flanders* (<https://www.vlaanderen.be/publicaties/beleidsplan-ruimte-vlaanderen-strategische-visie-geillustreerde-versie>), p. 36.

(c) Austrian government programme 2020-2024 (<https://www.bundeskanzleramt.gv.at/bundeskanzleramt/die-bundesregierung/regierungsdokumente.html>), p. 104.

(d) German sustainability strategy 2016 (<https://sustainabledevelopment-deutschland.github.io/en/11-1-a>).

(e) Un Luxembourg durable pour une meilleure qualité de vie (<https://environnement.public.lu/dam-assets/documents/developpement-durable/Un-Luxembourg-plus-durable-pour-une-meilleure-qualite-de-vie-2010.pdf>), p. 35.

(f) The law of agricultural and fishery modernization (<https://artificialisation.biodiversitetousvivants.fr>).

(g) Schweizerischer Bundesrat (2020, p. 22). This target implements SDG target 15.3 and the Seventh Environment Action Programme (no net land take). Compensation measures included, however, are based on qualitative requirements and measures rather than area related. Soil sealing is used as an indicator for land take until a national soil functions map is available.

In Italy, some soil sealing limits have been established at the municipality level:

- Brescia: minimum values for the extension of permeable green areas, ranging from 15% in the town centre to 35% in residential areas;
- Padua: 30-40% permeability in residential areas, 70% for parking areas and 90% for green public areas based on 'surface permeability' according to land use classes;
- Parma: minimum standards for 'surface permeability' of 75% for private gardens and 15-50% for commercial areas.

To truly understand soil sealing, it's interesting to assess it not only at the country level, but also in administrative regions, municipalities or ecoregions. This spatial distribution information could be relevant for landscape planning, supporting urban strategies aimed at containing soil sealing and connecting environmental sustainability and future urban development.

At the local level, urban morphological trends and expansions patterns, such as urban densification (new artificial sealing of soil within an urban area) and urban sprawling (low-density settlement

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expansion over larger regions), can be distinguished. Also in this case, thresholds for soil sealing, for instance for a defined land use pattern (core city, peri-urban area, rural area), have neither been defined nor implemented.

5.3.8. Further reading

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5.4. Greenhouse gas (GHG) and climate regulation including carbon sequestration

5.4.1. Selected indicators

Based on the previous evaluation of SERENA T2.3, the **Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP)** has been proposed as the pragmatic indicator of GHG assessment. NEP is defined as the difference between gross primary productivity (GPP) and total ecosystem respiration (in the gas flux measurements framework this is also called net ecosystem exchange, NEE).

5.4.2. Selected methodology:

The overall NEP calculation considers GPP, net primary productivity (NPP), autotrophic respiration (Ra) and heterotrophic respiration (Rh), i.e. ecosystem respiration (RECO) as follows:

$$\text{NEP} = \text{NPP} - \text{Rh}$$

$$\text{NPP} = \text{GPP} - \text{Ra},$$

$$\text{NEP} = \text{GPP} - \text{Ra} - \text{Rh} = \text{GPP} - (\text{Ra} + \text{Rh}), \text{ where } \text{Ra} + \text{Rh} = \text{RECO}$$

$$\text{NEP} = \text{GPP} - \text{RECO}$$

whereas in a detailed GHG flux analyses NEP is defined as the instantaneous measurement of net ecosystem exchange (NEE) where $\text{NEP} = -\text{NEE}$ measured on a per second basis).

Elaborated by: Eduardo Medina-Roldán, Liia Kukk, Sylwia Pindal, and the SERENA GHG Working Group

5.4.3. Data and harmonization

The development of the GHG indicator methodology analysis included several stages. Firstly, a whole documentation review based on the NEP applications from the different member states (MSs) as reported in T3.1. Within such internal review, it was considered that the NEP analyses/methods reported by the different SERENA MS were not suitable for further national/regional scale analysis, since they were mainly derived from data-intensive mechanistic models (the Inter-task Group suggestion was to avoid this). At a second stage, an “external” literature review was based on Web of Science (WOS) Platform through different queries (non-exhaustive, non-systematic). Here, global and EU-scale traditional climate-related statistical models, light use efficiency (LUE) models, ecosystem process models as well as more simple empirical models were further analysed. Although C-fix, CASA as well as several empirical models were selected as promising NEP models for developing the cookbook, it was concluded that their data requirements were too heavy for a cookbook (other Inter-task Group rule). This is why it was decided to develop a new empirical relation with spatially explicit variables; correlating the FLUXNET database (eddy covariance flux measurements) data with MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) terrestrial primary production products and climatic variables also in spatially-exhaustive databases. Fluxnet is a research network with detailed NEE measurements for several stations distributed all over the world (<https://fluxnet.org/sites/site-summary>) with measurements differing in temporal range between them (from one year to slightly

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more than a decade). Since our focus was relating MODIS products to Fluxnet measurements, we concentrated on the MOD17A2HGF GPP collection. Such values are based on the radiation use efficiency approach and represent composited 8-day interval observations where GPP is calculated and rendered at a 500 m spatial resolution (https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/documents/495/MOD17_User_Guide_V6.pdf). The availability of the MODIS products and of the Fluxnet database limited our empirical relation to the period 2001-2014 (when both Fluxnet and MODIS data are available). This time window determined that the date of other data products that were used should be close to those dates. Other attempts have been made to relate MODIS and Fluxnet GPP data (Verma et al. 2015, Verma et al. 2014), but here we add a recent soil moisture database to improve the relationship. The approach tried to minimise the use of command line/computing language tools (such as R, yet another suggestion to develop cookbooks), and it relies more strongly on open GIS tools.

5.4.4. Scope/output

The cookbook states a relation between the component of NEP in the form:

$$Y = B_i * X_i$$

The current GHG cookbook is based on: (1) a statistical empirical relationship between the Fluxnet GPP database and MODIS GPP products with environmental covariates, only for areas growing wheat. Note that here, NEE (and thus NEP) does not include the C as part of GPP exported with the harvest of the crop, and this should be included if one wants to determine the C emissions separately. The empirical relation is a multiple regression that includes only significant terms, mainly average temperature (average of monthly minimum and maximum temperature), and soil moisture content. Other spatial environmental covariates such as precipitation were not statistically significant and were thus left out. (2) The second relation to derive ecosystem respiration (RECO) was done with a thermal performance model that uses only average temperature to calculate RECO. The first large part of the cookbook considers the GPP analysis. GPP evaluation includes the average temperature and soil moisture raster analysis (layers reprojection etc.) in QGIS, MODIS GPP products conversion to raster format and resampling temperature and soil moisture in R package, and further empirical GPP calculation of harmonized raster layers in QGIS.

In the second step of the NEP analysis, the ecosystem respiration (RECO) is calculated, and the final NEP calculation is done by subtracting RECO from GPP. The final, third step is the linking of the results to the EU 2018 crop layer where land cover is equal to wheat croplands as this is the kind of vegetation used to develop the empirical model.

Relate the results to the EU 2018 crop layer

Table D.2.3.2.11 below provides a brief description of the data to be used. Note that the indicator will be calculated for the year 2014 only in this example. This is because this is the last year when Fluxnet data are available and are close to the date for the EU 2018 crop types layer. This assumes that the value space (NEP and the other environmental variables) for which the statistical relationship was derived did not change significantly for 2018 (an assumption that seems reasonable).

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Table D.2.3.2.11: Data requirements and how to acquire them

Data	Description	Variable	Units	Spatial resolution	Dates	CRS	File format	Comments	How to get it?
MODIS MOD17A2HG F Collection	8-day composite GPP product derived from the MODIS algorithm (a light absorption efficiency family)	GPP	kgC/m ² /8day	500 m	2001-2014	Sinusoidal	Raster	The version 6 of the collection was decommissioned from the LP DAAC Centre, yet it is the one used on this cookbook as the new version 6.1 dates are not in the temporal range of the Fluxnet data	From R MODIRTools package ¹
Daily soil moisture data derived from Zhang et al. 2023	Daily volumetric soil moisture	Wv	g ³ of moisture per g ³ soil	1000 m	2014	Sinusoidal, but it has its own definition	Raster	The dataset has some important gaps in high latitude areas. As a result, gap filling needs to be carried out with long-term year average	From Teams sharepoint ²
Daily soil moisture data CRS information	CRS of the moisture dataset in which other variables need to be projected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	text	Wkt file	From Teams sharepoint ²
World Climate tmax	Maximum monthly temperature	WClim tmax	°C	2.5' (around 4600 m at the low EU latitudes)	2014	WGS84	Raster	A daily database could be eventually be used	From Teams sharepoint ³
World Climate tmin	Minimum monthly temperature	WClim tmin	°C	2.5' (around 4600 m at the low EU latitudes)	2014	WGS84	Raster	A daily database could be eventually be used	From Teams sharepoint ⁴
EU 2018 croplands	Derived from Sentinel-1 and LUCAS 2018 observations, filtered here for wheat	EU18	Crop classes (unitless)	10 m	2018	WTRS89-Extended / LAEA Europe	Raster	The data layer is either distributed as a heavy raster file (7 Gb), or as 1600 raster tiles. Because of this, 23x23 tiles were created, and converted to vector format to be used in the final mask for rendering the final indicator spatial distribution	From Teams sharepoint ⁵
Political regional boundaries	Region to be analysed	Area of interest	unitless	Variable and particular for each MS	Variable	Variable	Vector	It is suggested to reproject the AOI to match with soil moisture layer	To be acquired by each MS

¹Step 6 in the cookbook

²Full address link to folder: https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/SERENAEJP-SOIL/Documenti%20condivisi/General/WGs/Cookbook/CIReg_GHG/data_for_application/moisture_data?csf=1&web=1&e=KpWgfp

³Full address link to folder: https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/SERENAEJP-SOIL/Documenti%20condivisi/General/WGs/Cookbook/CIReg_GHG/data_for_application/WorldClim_tempdata?csf=1&web=1&e=2MkH Mp

⁴Full address link to folder: https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/SERENAEJP-SOIL/Documenti%20condivisi/General/WGs/Cookbook/CIReg_GHG/data_for_application/WorldClim_tempdata?csf=1&web=1&e=2MkH Mp

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⁵Full address link to folder: [https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/SERENAEJP-SOIL/Documenti%20condivisi/General/WGs/Cookbook/CIReg_GHG/data for application/EU2018_croplandmap_wheat?csf=1&web=1&e=Yz9stt](https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/SERENAEJP-SOIL/Documenti%20condivisi/General/WGs/Cookbook/CIReg_GHG/data%20for%20application/EU2018_croplandmap_wheat?csf=1&web=1&e=Yz9stt)

5.4.5. Software

The cookbook has as little command code as possible, as it was decided to use an open source GIS desktop version to do most of the job. However, some steps require the use of R (mainly for downloading MODIS products, and for resampling spatial rasters). Yet, it requires some basic GIS and R familiarity. For instance, for GIS working with projections and reprojections. For R, starting a session in a working directory, stating the patch to files to be uploaded, among others.

- A recent installation of R: <https://cran.r-project.org/> (installation instructions can be found in the website, for Windows: <https://cran.r-project.org/doc/manuals/r-patched/R-admin.html#Installing-R-under-Windows>). Packages RMODISTools (Tuck et al., 2014) and R terra (Hijmans et al., 2022) should be installed. For installing packages within R see: <https://cran.r-project.org/doc/manuals/r-patched/R-admin.html#Installing-packages> (you just need to have admin rights and run command “install.packages()” within your R session). For example, use `install.packages('RMODISTools')` and `install.packages('terra')` to install both packages separately. When selecting a CRAN mirror, choose a location near you for faster downloads.
- Detailed information about QGIS is available at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/QGIS>. A recent installation of QGIS: qgis.org In Windows you can install either the stand alone installation Desktop version: <https://qgis.org/downloads/QGIS-OSGeo4W-3.36.0-1.msi>, but the installation with GRASS is highly recommended (check installation options) as it provides some more efficient algorithms for some of the tasks. Double check system requirements as they might vary for different operating systems. The latest version of QGIS also includes GRASS and SAGA GIS (both downloaded with QGIS and included in the QGIS folder).

5.4.6. Application

The method relies on the empirical relation derived from spatially explicit products of MODIS GPP (Running and Zhao 2019) and other co-variates with Fluxnet (FLUXNET 2023) measures in stations with historical land cover with wheat (even if in rotation with other crops). More details of the development of such relation are shown somewhere else (Appendix I can be consulted here: [Link to Zenodo Repository](#)). The empirical relation should not be seen as an explanatory one, but just an empirical relation given the covariates and datasets used. A number of different possible ways to produce the final result could have been picked (Fig. D.2.3.2.16), but here the order is such that a single R session is used to produce some few estimates of the indicator (3 or 4 each time⁶⁰¹). A more

¹An approach to produce an annual estimate is possible, but it would be more practical to do it within a code environment. Also, it was seen the annual indicator accumulates error.

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general R script to derive NEP for the whole number of 8-d periods in a whole year and summarise them statistically has been designed for those more familiar with R [Link to Zenodo Repository](#)

Figure D.2.3.2.16: Flowchart of the main steps used to derive the estimates of GPP, RECO, and NEP, as well as the spatialization of NEP.

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First part: GPP

Step1. Define an area of interest.

This is needed to set the area for which MODIS products will be downloaded. The estimates of GPP are derived from local NEE observations scale up to a broader spatial extent by the spatially exhaustive covariates. This, and the fact that some of the data layers are rather heavy, makes it more appropriate for analysis of regional extensions (as opposed to National-level extensions for larger countries). The example included in this cookbook are for the area of the lowland plains of the Emilia-Romagna region (ERR) in N Italy. This region has a WE extent of around 280 km and a NS one of around 150 km. We need the extension of the area of interest to determine the extension of the MODIS GPP products to use, which in turn will define the spatial extent in which the analysis will be carried out. Because there is a 200 km x 200 km limit on the extent in which the MODIS GPP products can be downloaded in R MODISTools (the library used to automatize the process), one has to figure out the number of MODIS tiles to be downloaded for larger areas, and their spatial location and extent to cover the AOI (area of interest). If your AOI is smaller than 200x200 km you can skip this step. In the example below for Emilia-Romagna, this was done with QGIS ('QGIS Desktop' from the downloaded folder). The ERR border area (CRS:WGS84) is imported into QGIS, its extent is defined by the corners of the region (this can be seen in the layer properties) (Figs. D.2.3.2.17 and D.2.3.2.18). Note that this info will be used later in step 6, so keep it in a folder you can easily find.

Fig. D.2.3.2.17: Selecting AOI layer properties (in WGS84) to see its spatial extent.

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Fig. D.2.3.2.18: AOI layer properties information showing spatial extent.

With the extent information, the information on the location and extension to acquire the MODIS products can be obtained by dividing the area into sectors (in the ERR example it is 2 sectors, with the information of the coordinates in the location of two quarters of the AOI extent done using a vector point layer, Fig. D.2.3.2.19).

Fig. D.2.3.2.19: Example of determining location of coordinates and extension of tiles to acquire MODIS products.

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A polygon can even be created with the AOI extent to clip the World Climate rasters later on to process them more quickly (Figs. D.2.3.2.20- D.2.3.2.22).

Fig. D.2.3.2.20: Creating a polygon that covers the AOI that can be then used for clipping other rasters I.

Fig. D.2.3.2.21: Creating a polygon that covers the AOI that can be then used for clipping other rasters II.

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Fig. D.2.3.2.22: Creating a polygon that covers the AOI that can be then used for clipping other rasters III.

Step 2. Keep in mind the number of period(s) to be analysed

This(these) period(s) is(are) the 8-day dates that coincide with the calendar days when MODIS products are available (Table D.2.3.2.12). The ranking of indicators exercise indicated that NEP should be estimated on an annual basis. This implies that the whole 45 8-d periods should be estimated and summed up to obtain the indicator on an annual basis. However, analyses showed that the small deviations from each 8-d NEP estimation over accumulate unacceptably when the 8-d periods are aggregated to calculate annual NEP. Two alternatives were proposed with the current statistical approach developed. (1) To single out single 8-d periods that can be considered representative of the variation in the annual process (e.g., summer peaks, and winter lows), For this it is recommended to do 3-4 8-d periods each time if using GIS, instead of the 45 for data management considerations, but each partner can decide on this. This estimation focuses only on 2014 data to be close to the last publicly available observations of Fluxnet (Pastorello et al., 2020) and the EU 2018 crops map (d'Andrimont et al., 2021). The second approach is more data intensive, and as such it is based on an R script. In this second approach, long-term variation in NEP values (2010-2014) are averaged and their central and dispersion values can be used to single out the representative single 8-d periods that capture the annual variation in NEP (see D3.3 example for Italy for more details) Table D.2.3.2.12 also offers information on the period when soil moisture rasters should be averaged, and the months to use for World Climate products too. For the example shown here, a single period of January was selected, with end-date on January 9th. With this information one must select the day of year when soil moisture products need to be averaged (days of year 2-9) and then months of the World Climate dataset to be used (January in this case). If the other two periods of January were going to be done (those ending on 17th and 25th), the dates to average the

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moisture data would be: 10th -17th, and 18th-25th, whereas the climate data to be used would be still those corresponding to January.

Table D.2.3.2.12: Information on the periods when MODIS GPP products are available for 2014, and the time of other datasets to be used for estimating GPP. This information applies to all regions, not only to the example.

Dates of MODIS 2014 GPP product	Year	month	Day	Month-Day	Days to average raster soil moisture data	Equivalent days of year soil moisture data		Wclim data to use (maximum temperature and minimum temperature)
						From	To	
2014-01-09	2014	1	9	01-09	Jan 02 to 09	2	9	Jan
2014-01-17	2014	1	17	01-17	Jan 10 to 17	10	17	Jan
2014-01-25	2014	1	25	01-25	Jan 18 to 25	18	25	Jan
2014-02-02	2014	2	2	02-02	Jan 26 to Feb 02	26	33	Jan
2014-02-10	2014	2	10	02-10	Feb 03 to Feb 10	34	41	Feb
2014-02-18	2014	2	18	02-18	Feb 11 to Feb 18	42	49	Feb
2014-02-26	2014	2	26	02-26	Feb 19 to Feb 26	50	57	Feb
2014-03-06	2014	3	6	03-06	Feb 27 to March 06	58	65	March
2014-03-14	2014	3	14	03-14	March 07 to March 14	66	73	March
2014-03-22	2014	3	22	03-22	March 15 to March 22	74	81	March
2014-03-30	2014	3	30	03-30	March 23 to March 30	82	89	March
2014-04-07	2014	4	7	04-07	March 31 to April 7	90	97	April
2014-04-15	2014	4	15	04-15	April 08 to April 15	98	105	April
2014-04-23	2014	4	23	04-23	April 16 to April 23	106	113	April
2014-05-01	2014	5	1	05-01	April 24 to May 01	114	121	April
2014-05-09	2014	5	9	05-09	May 02 to May 09	122	129	May
2014-05-17	2014	5	17	05-17	May 10 to May 17	130	137	May
2014-05-25	2014	5	25	05-25	May 18 to May 25	138	145	May
2014-06-02	2014	6	2	06-02	May 25 to June 02	146	153	May
2014-06-10	2014	6	10	06-10	June 03 to June 10	154	161	June
2014-06-18	2014	6	18	06-18	June 11 to June 18	162	169	June
2014-06-26	2014	6	26	06-26	June 19 to June 26	170	177	June
2014-07-04	2014	7	4	07-04	June 27 to July 04	178	185	July
2014-07-12	2014	7	12	07-12	July 05 to July 12	186	193	July
2014-07-20	2014	7	20	07-20	July 13 to July 20	194	201	July
2014-07-28	2014	7	28	07-28	July 21 to July 28	202	209	July
2014-08-05	2014	8	5	08-05	July 28 to August 05	210	217	August
2014-08-13	2014	8	13	08-13	August 06 to August 13	218	225	August
2014-08-21	2014	8	21	08-21	August 14 to August 21	226	233	August
2014-08-29	2014	8	29	08-29	August 22 to August 29	234	241	August
2014-09-06	2014	9	6	09-06	August 30 to September 06	242	249	September
2014-09-14	2014	9	14	09-14	September 07 to September 14	250	257	September
2014-09-22	2014	9	22	09-22	September 15 to September 22	258	265	September
2014-09-30	2014	9	30	09-30	September 23 to September 30	266	273	September
2014-10-08	2014	10	8	10-08	October 01 to October 08	274	281	October
2014-10-16	2014	10	16	10-16	October 09 to October 16	282	289	October
2014-10-24	2014	10	24	10-24	October 17 to October 24	290	297	October
2014-11-01	2014	11	1	11-01	October 25 to November 01	298	305	October
2014-11-09	2014	11	9	11-09	November 02 to November 09	306	313	November
2014-11-17	2014	11	17	11-17	November 10 to November 17	314	321	November
2014-11-25	2014	11	25	11-25	November 18 to November 25	322	329	November
2014-12-03	2014	12	3	12-03	November 26 to December 03	330	337	November
2014-12-11	2014	12	11	12-11	December 04 to December 11	338	345	December
2014-12-19	2014	12	19	12-19	December 12 to December 19	346	353	December
2014-12-27	2014	12	27	12-27	December 20 to December 27	354	361	December

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Step 3. Produce average temperature raster(s) from World Climate maximum and minimum temperature rasters

Load to QGIS the World Climate maximum and minimum temperature rasters that correspond to the period(s) selected (in the example case, this corresponds to January). Optionally, the polygon with the AOI extent generated before as shown in Figs. D.2.3.2.20-D.2.3.2.22 can be used to clip the World Climate data (Figs. D.2.3.2.23-D.2.3.2.26) with the option **Clip Raster by Mask Layer** in the **Raster** option of the menu before performing raster algebra operations to make the processes quicker (including reprojection and import into R). QGIS has the option to do batch operations so that both maximum and minimum temperatures can be clipped at the same time (Figs. D.2.3.2.23-D.2.3.2.26)*.

Figure D.2.3.2.23: Clipping World Climate temperature rasters with the polygon with the AOI extent created before.

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Figure D.2.3.2.24: The clipping can be processed as a batch process where more than one raster can be clipped at once.

** If both raster maps as well as polygons (AOI boarder and well as polygon with the AOI extent) do not appear in the same window, open all layers one by one and save polygons with the same coordinate system as raster maps (EPSG:4326 - WGS 84): select layer, right click Export, Save features as etc. Do not forget to select the folder and add file name within the option File name.*

Figure D.2.3.2.25: As a batch process, several rasters can be used as input layers and processed at once by clicking on the add row option (plus sign).

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Figure D.2.3.2.26: Save the World Climate temperature clips in a folder whose location you are aware of, otherwise the layers will be saved only temporarily*.

* If the system gives an error notice, the common problems could be one of the following: layer edits are not saved (select and save layer edits), layer is in RAM memory (export the layer and save permanently in the folder), attribute table includes additional features (open the attribute table with the right click on the layer and delete additional features, save layer edits)

Once you have the temperature clips (recommend it) or with the full temperature raster files, go to the **Raster** option in the menu and click on **Raster Calculator**, a pop-up window will come where you need to introduce the information to do the average of the temperature layers (Figure D.2.3.2.27). Here you must define your temperature raster inputs, the operation to be performed, and the location and name of the output raster.

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Figure D.2.3.2.27: Raster calculator showing the required elements to produce an average temperature layer for the AOI (raster input layers, raster operation, and raster output).

Figure D.2.3.2.28: Result of the raster calculator averaging temperature clipped layers.

Step 4. Reproject average temperature raster(s)

The input data used have different coordinate reference system specifications (see Table D.2.3.2.12). This their reprojection is needed. Since MODIS and the soil moisture data are in the sinusoidal

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projection (equal-area), it is more practical to reproject all other CRS (coordinate reference system) into it. To do so a wkt file with the soil moisture CRS specification is provided (Table D.2.3.2.12). Detailed instructions on how to work with projections in QGIS are given here:

https://docs.qgis.org/3.28/en/docs/user_manual/working_with_projections/working_with_projections.html. Here for brevity, download the wkt file (“moisture_dataset.wkt”) in a directory. In QGIS go to **Options** in the **Settings** option of the menu (Figure D.2.3.2.29).

Figure D.2.3.2.29: Selecting the Options item from menu.

In the pop-up window, go to **User Defined CRS** (Fig. 15), and click on the plus sign to add a new user defined CRS. Name the new CRS (in the example in Figure D.2.3.2.30, this is “moisture_data_CRS”). The format should be WKT, and within the text box, you should copy (e.g. from WKT opened in Microsoft Notepad) and paste the contents of the wkt file “moisture_dataset.wkt” provided in the sharepoint (large highlighted rectangle in Figure D.2.3.2.30). Click on OK and this will create the CRS we will use.

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Figure D.2.3.2.30: Defining a user CRS in QGIS.

Once the CRS has been created, select **Warp (Reproject)** from the **Raster** menu (Figure D.2.3.2.31):

Figure D.2.3.2.31: Reprojecting the World Climate raster layer.

In the reprojection pop up window define (1) the input raster to be reprojected (the average temperature raster clip), (2) the reprojected raster output (name and directory), (3) the resampling method (in this case bilinear as the input is numeric), and (4) the target CRS created from the WKT file (Figure D.2.3.2.32).

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Figure D.2.3.2.32: Reprojecting pop-up window, with the options that need to be defined.

In the target CRS definition part, select **Predefined CRS** (Figure D.2.3.2.33).

Figure D.2.3.2.33: Selecting CRS for reprojecting average temperature.

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Different **Predefined CRS** options are shown (Figure D.2.3.2.34), scroll all the way down until the **User Defined Coordinate Systems** option appears; then select the CRS defined from the WTK file, go back to the main reprojection options (green arrow) and run the reprojection.

Figure D.2.3.2.34: Selecting the User Defined Coordinate System defined before for reprojecting average temperature.

Step 5. Average soil moisture rasters

To find the soil moisture rasters to be used for a particular AOI, check the tiles organization of the product (Figure D.2.3.2.35. it is the same as that used by MODIS GPP products). The tiles are organized by row (h) and column (v) numbers. For the example of the Emilia-Romagna Region in the example, the tile corresponds to h18v04.

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Figure D.2.3.2.35: Organisation of the sinusoidal projection tiles (from Lyapustin et al., 2018).

The soil moisture raster files are named following this row/column number convention, plus the day of the year. Thus, for the first period of the year the soil moisture rasters correspond to days of the year 02-09; and the corresponding soil moisture files for the ERR are sm_2014002_h18v04.tif all the way to sm_2014009_h18v04.tif. Just as it was shown for the raster calculations with temperature (Figure D.2.3.2.36), load the soil moisture rasters in QGIS for the particular period(s) being evaluated (Table D.2.3.2.12) and create the soil moisture average(s). Note that the soil moisture product has significant spatial and temporal gaps (specially for Northern regions). Such spatial gaps might be filled up, for instance by using simple average-distance based algorithms (one not covered here is implemented in GRASS GIS: <https://grass.osgeo.org/grass84/manuals/r.fill.stats.html>)-The temporal gaps might be more important since they might constitute an obstacle to determine NEP at a particular 8-d period (as a whole day or set of days might be missing in the data). If this is the case, one has to create the rasters for the missing dates through the raster calculator in QGIS or in R. One way to do so is by averaging a number of moisture rasters depending on their availability in the moisture dataset. For instance, if a day is missing and that date is available for several years, one can use the average of that date for several years. If there is no information for the day missing in other years, then one can use monthly averages, etc.

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Figure D.2.3.2.36: Raster calculation example for the first January period (Table 2) of sinusoidal tiles (Fig. 20) that correspond to the ERR. Highlighted are the input raster layers, the raster operation to average, and the output layer.

Step 6. Acquire MODIS GPP products with R MODISTools package and convert them to raster

The next step is within the R environment. It is recommended to have clear input and output folders within the directory where the session is being run in advance to make it easier to identify where the outputs/inputs are. Once you have started the R session, the R code for obtaining the MODIS products (in this case for the settings of the ERR) can be seen in the code-box below (you need to adjust the settings to your own AOI). MODISTools allows gathering MODIS products without the need to sign up in advance (e.g., to the LP DAAC centre). You can copy paste the code adjusting the settings for your own AOI spatial extent. The code will cater the MODIS data for all 8-d periods.

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```

# Load required packages
require(MODISTools)
require(terra)

subset.IT.ER.2014.1 <- mt_subset(product = "MOD17A2HGF", ##### Change
country/location name for location/country's name
lat = 44.516795, ##### Change for window's center lat, this is the central lat of your
area's windows
lon = 10.1704315, ##### Change for window's center long, this is the central long of
your area's windows
km_lr = 80, ##### It has to be determined first on the political area extent
km_ab = 85,
band = "Gpp_500m",
start = "2014-01-02", ##### Adjust depending on partner's interest, but more data will
take considerable time and computing power to handle them
end = "2014-12-31", ##### Adjust depending on country's interest
site_name="IT-ER", ##### Change depending on location/country's name
progress = FALSE) ##### Note this dataset is overwritten each time the R environemnt
is closed

subset.IT.ER.2014.2 <- mt_subset(product = "MOD17A2HGF", ##### Change
country/location name for location/country's name
lat = 44.516795, ##### Change for window's centre lat, this is the central lat of one of
your area's quarter sector
lon = 11.8947225, ##### Change for window's center long, this is the central long of
your area's windows
km_lr = 80,
km_ab = 85,
band = "Gpp_500m",
start = "2014-01-02", ##### Adjust depending on partner's interest, but more data will
take considerable time and computing power to handle them
end = "2014-12-31", ##### Adjust depending on country's interest
site_name="IT-ER", ##### Change depending on location/country's name
progress = FALSE) ##### Note this dataset is overwritten each time the R environment
is closed

# Convert products to rasters (the number of raster layers being equal to dates stated
and with data present in the database)
IT.ER.MODIS2014.r1 <- mt_to_terra(df = subset.IT.ER.2014.1)
IT.ER.MODIS2014.r2 <- mt_to_terra(df = subset.IT.ER.2014.2)

# Merge MODIS rasters
IT.ER.MODIS2014.r <- merge(IT.ER.MODIS2014.r1,IT.ER.MODIS2014.r2)

# Check out created objects

```

Step 7. Set acquired MODIS products not defined land cover classes (e.g., urban) to NULL

The acquired MODIS products are set a cell value of ≥ 3 to urban and other land covers for which GPP values are not applicable. Such land covers need to be set to NULL (NA in script) before exporting them out from the R environment. See code-box below for the cookbook example on how to do it within the same R session (if you leave the R session, data will be lost unless saved, and the libraires will have to be reloaded).

```
#Setting urban (and similar) land covers to NULL for MODIS products before
exporting. MODIS products set values for land covers such as urban or water
bodies to  $\geq 3$  (before rescaling).

m <- c(3, 4, NA) # Creating matrix stating that values among 3 and 4 will be set
to NA

rclmat <- matrix(m, ncol=3, byrow=TRUE) # Creating matrix

IT.ER.MODIS2014.nulls <- classify(IT.ER.MODIS2014.r,rclmat) #Reclassifying
raster layers 1 to 3. Thsi value has to be adjusted depending on the number of
layers of the MODIS raster object acquired with RMODISTools

IT.RER.MODIS2014.nulls.sc <- IT.RER.MODIS2014.nulls/10 #####scale GPP
MODIS to 1/10, this is the source of the previus error, this corrects it. Negative,
this was only a source of error, the othe one has been detected and corrected in
this new version of the script (08/07/2024). This scaling factor is kept for avoiding
further confusion.
```

Step 8. Resample temperature and soil moisture rasters to fit with MODIS products

The input files produced before need to be loaded into the R session: (1) the reprojected average temperature raster(s) derived from steps 3-4, and (2) the average soil moisture raster(s) derived from step 5. This is because they need to be resampled to a similar spatial structure as the MODIS products to be able to apply the raster operations. The terra package in R performs this operation using the bilinear interpolation as default for rasters with numeric data. Again, pay attention to where the input files are (path to folders and name of files), and where the output files (path to folders and name of files) will be saved as part the R session.

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```
# Import 8-days averaged moisture raster from step 5 for resampling.
IT.ER.moistavg.2014.Jan09 <- rast("/yourPathtoInputDirectory/h18v04_02-09Jan_avg.tif") #You need to
adjust the path depending on your system and the directory where the file is. The one shown is for a Linux
example. Another path example is as follows: <- rast("C:\\Backup\\Desktop\\...")

## Resampling soil moisture raster
IT.ER.moistavg.2014.Jan09.rsmpl <- resample(IT.ER.moistavg.2014.Jan09,IT.ER.MODIS2014.Jan) # First raster
is the one which spatial structure will be equalised with that of the second one

### Loading reprojected average temperature raster from World Climate
IT.ER.WClim.tavg2014.Jan <- rast("/yourPathtoInputDirectory/tavg_clipped_rprj_nn.tif") # Same, adjust path
and file name according to where you have the file

## Resampling with MODIS layer as in the soil moisture case above
IT.ER.WClim.tavg2014.Jan.rsmpl <- resample(IT.ER.WClim.tavg2014.Jan,IT.ER.MODIS2014.Jan)
```

Step 9. Export all rasters outside the R environment

Now the products are ready to work outside R. For exporting them outside the R environment see code-box below.

```
# Write rasters to disk in the working directory (or change path if you want other directory)
# Writing MODIS raster
writeRaster(IT.ER.MODIS2014.nulls.sc,"IT_ER_MODIS_GPP2014.tif",overwrite=TRUE) # Another example is
as follows: writeRaster(your_raster, filename = "path/to/your/output/folder/output_name.tif", overwrite =
TRUE). Note that path to folders is the folder where the raster will be saved

# Writing resampled 8-d averaged soil moisture raster
writeRaster(IT.ER.moistavg.2014.Jan09.rsmpl,"IT_ER_moistavg_2014_Jan09rsmpl.tif",overwrite=TRUE)
# Writing reprojected and resampled World Climate average monthly temperature raster
writeRaster(IT.ER.WClim.tavg2014.Jan.rsmpl,"IT_ER_WClim.pr2014.Jan.rsmpl.tif",overwrite=TRUE)
```

Step 10. Raster calculation using the empirical relationship between FLuxnet GPP and spatial covariates

Details on the derivation of the empirical relation are given somewhere else [Link to Zenodo Repository](#) Again, note that the relationship does not imply necessarily causation, but just an empirical relation under the covariates' space. The derived multiple linear regression using all the Fluxnet sites, once correlated covariates were replaced (this is minimum and maximum monthly

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temperature replaced with average temperature), and the non-significant ones in a preliminary model were eliminated is:

$$GPP = 10.09835 + 1.39434 \times MOD \times 1000 - 0.35939 \times mtavg - 0.01794 \times mtavg^2 - 27.16783 \times \frac{Wv}{1000}$$

Where GPP is the estimate of the equivalent Fluxnet 8-d GPP (in $gC\ m^{-2}$ in 8 days), MOD is MODIS 8-d GPP as output from steps 8-9, mtavg is the average monthly temperature (in the example January average monthly temperature), and Wv is the 8-d average soil volumetric moisture. Load into QGIS the corresponding raster layers exported from R in step 9 and use the empirical relation to calculate the GPP estimate (Figure D.2.3.2.37). Be careful how you introduce the terms in the raster calculator (to be more certain you might produce first single terms rasters, e.g., $(1.39434) \times (MOD \times 10000)$, and then sum them all up) as you might produce spurious calculations.

Figure D.2.3.2.37: Raster calculator in QGIS with the empirical relation among covariates to produce the GPP indicator.

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Figure D.2.3.2.38: Results of the example of the ERR GPP for the first 8 days period in January.

The extreme (maximum and minimum) values from which the CO2 flux relationships were derived can be found in Table D.2.3.2.13. Calculations should not be extrapolated outside the extremes used to fit the models as this can produce values with no physical sense (in the current example, negative values of GPP). An additional sub-step is needed to get rid of such spurious GPP values in the layer just generated.

Table D.2.3.2.13: Extreme and mean values of the variables used to fit the empirical relation for GPP

Variable	Maximum	Minimum	Average
8-d Fluxnet GPP (gCm ⁻² in 8 days)	177.92	0	26.38
8-d MODIS GPP	92.40	0	21.18
World Climate monthly average temperature (°C)	32.00	-11.0	10.9
Volumetric soil moisture (cm ³ cm ⁻³)	0.36	0.04	0.22
8-d Fluxnet RECO (gC m ⁻² in 8 days)	105.34	0.17	21.02
8-d Fluxnet NEP (gC m ⁻² in 8 days)	102.05	-50.43	5.13

For this cleaning up sub-step we create a new raster layer that recognises negative values as zeros (FALSE), and positive ones as one (TRUE) to be used as a kind of mask. This is done in the raster calculator just setting the values to be recognised as TRUE ("GPP_raster.tif >= 0", Figures D.2.3.2.39-D.2.3.2.40). The expression "GPP_raster.tif >= 0" is used to create a binary raster layer where each pixel is assigned a value of 1 if the corresponding pixel value in the "GPP_raster.tif" raster layer is greater than or equal to zero, and a value of 0 otherwise. Keep this logical raster layer as it will also be used for the calculation of NEP in the next step.

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Figure D.2.3.2.39: Creation of a logical raster (values equal to 1 and zero) to filter out negative values of GPP.

Figure D.2.3.2.40: Resulting logical raster with values only equal either to 1 or zero (in the small panel a spatial query producing a value of zero is shown).

To filter the negative values out of the original GPP layer, do another raster calculation this time multiplying the original GPP raster layer with the logical raster (Figure D.2.3.2.41). The resulting raster is the GPP layer with negatives values filtered out (Figure D.2.3.2.42). However, keep in mind that in the current state, the output layer containing 0 contains both the 0*1 from the calculations

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(actual GPP values 0) and the multiplication of negative values by 0 (from the grid calculation expression in Figure D.2.3.2.41). This knowledge will be used in the following steps (Figures D.2.3.2.44- D.2.3.2.47) to include in the final NEP map layer those values where GPP was actually zero and their contribution to the NEP indicator is valid.

Figure D.2.3.2.41: Raster calculation to filter out negative GPP values among the original GPP output (Figure D.2.3.2.38) with the logical raster with values of only 1 and zero (Figure D.2.3.2.40).

Figure D.2.3.2.42: Output GPP raster with GPP negative values filtered out (note negative values at original layer have been set to zero).

Step 11. Calculating NEP by subtracting RECO to GPP

Ecosystem respiration (RECO) was modelled through a thermal performance approach (Padfield et al., 2021) to take advantage of the relation between RECO and average monthly temperature (see Appendix for more details: [Link to Zenodo Repository](#)) This is shown in the formula below. Note once more that the approach is data-dependent, and not mechanistic, since the depression of respiration

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at the high end of monthly temperatures in the dataset deserves further investigation, and this is likely to be site-dependent.

$$RECO = 38.86 \cdot e^{-0.5 \left(\frac{mtavg - 18.39}{5.99} \right)^{1.14}}$$

RECO is ecosystem respiration (in gC m⁻² in 8 days), and mtavg is the average monthly temperature. Pay attention to how the formula is inserted to avoid spurious values (it is recommended to start up from the most inner parenthesis outwards).

Once the GPP raster with negative values filtered out is ready (Figure D.2.3.2.42), the calculation of NEP can be done in a single step. For this upload the reprojected average temperature raster to QGIS (the resampled product produced from steps 4 and 8), and calculate NEP in the raster calculator as NEP = GPP-RECO

where NEP is equal to net ecosystem productivity (in gC m⁻² in 8 days), GPP is GPP with negative values filtered out, and RECO is derived from the formula shown above.

Figure D.2.3.2.43: 28. Calculation of NEP.

Those locations that showed negative values of GPP must be filtered out (they do not have physical meaning) to separate them from real locations where GPP was zero and their contribution to the NEP indicator is valid. These filtering out operations for both GPP (Figures D.2.3.2.39-D.2.3.2.41) and NEP values (Figs. 29-32) will have to be applied to each of the weekly calculations. For the NEP indicator, the logical raster layer (Figures D.2.3.2.39-D.2.3.2.41) where values are equal to zero need to be made NULL. This is done with the *r.null* operation in QGIS (remember you can find it by typing at the processing search bar, Figure D.2.3.2.44).

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Figure D.2.3.2.44: Process r.null.

Click on the r.null operation and fill in the pop-up window fields with the appropriate values (Figure D.2.3.2.45).

Figure D.2.3.2.45: Values for the fields of the r.null operation to filter out locations for which GPP was negative. Note the zero value is the one set to NULL.

Finally, multiply the NEP raster layer with this raster with NULL locations in the raster calculator (Figure D.2.3.2.46). This creates the valid NEP output raster layer (Figure D.2.3.2.47). Ideally the indicator should be calculated for a whole year by summing up all NEP for each 8-d periods, but as

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mentioned before this causes error accumulation in the indicator annual value, so singling out representative 8-d periods is considered an acceptable option for now.

Figure D.2.3.2.46: Raster calculator for deriving filtered NEP values from NEP produced in the calculation (Fig. 28) times the raster with null values when GPP was negative.

Figure D.2.3.2.47: Filtered NEP values.

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Step 12. Relate the results to the EU 2018 crop layer

The empirical relation among variables was performed for stations where wheat has been grown (either on its own or in rotation with other crops, Jiang et al., 2021). Given the uncertainties associated to GPP estimates for other photosynthetic pathways (C4), and other vegetation structures (shrubs, trees) (Yao et al., 2018), it is strongly recommended to express the results only for locations with records of this crop land cover within the EU regions. Thus, the last step involves to spatialise the calculated NEP indicator using the EU 2018 crops layer (d'Andrimont et al., 2021, the 2018 EU crop product is the closest in time to the end of Fluxnet open data in 2014). Ideally the spatialisation should be done with the calculated annual indicator (annual NEP, but this annual indicator accumulates error). Here, the example uses the 8-days filtered NEP calculated in the previous steps (Figure D.2.3.2.43). The finer-scale spatialisation is done by cutting the filtered NEP indicator (Figure D.2.3.2.47) with the EU 2018 crops layer based on your AOI in QGIS. The original EU 2018 crops layer has been reclassified in GRASS GIS to select only wheat, and it has been made available in 23x23 raster tiles to be downloaded from the sharepoint (Figure D.2.3.2.48, Table D.2.3.2.11). To identify the tile(s) that correspond to your AOI, determine the column (vertical) and row (horizontal) number combination in Figure D.2.3.2.48. Based on this you can download the corresponding tiles to your system and then to QGIS.

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Figure D.2.3.2.48: Tiled EU 2018 crops map.

Additionally, the tiles for countries that signed up for application of the cookbook can be found in Table D.2.3.2.14. Tiles shown in Table D.2.3.2.14 are available in the sharepoint. For other partners who want to apply the cookbook, you can write to the development team to get the corresponding tiles. For the example of the Emilia-Romagna region, the tiles correspond to tiles 1610 (row 16, column 10), 1710 and 1711.

The raster tiles corresponding to the AOI are downloaded from the sharepoint and loaded into QGIS (Figure D.2.3.2.49). A reprojected version of your AOI administrative borders (reprojected to the moisture wkt specifications, see step 4 in detail) can also be loaded (Figure D.2.3.2.50). Each EU-crop-2018 tile raster has to be converted to a logical raster (only 1 or zero, Figure D.2.3.2.51), then reclassified (wheat areas set to 1, others to NULL, Figure D.2.3.2.52), then vectorised (Figures D.2.3.2.53- D.2.3.2.58), reprojected (when saving the created vector, Figure D.2.3.2.58), and merged with other tiles (Figures D.2.3.2.59-D.2.3.2.61). Finally, a zonal statistics operation with these merged

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vector layers is performed to assign NEP filtered values to the wheat polygons (either common or durum wheat).

Table D.2.3.2.14: EU 2018 crop raster tiles for countries that signed up for the cookbook application.

Country	Austria	Estonia	France	Italy	Poland	Ireland	Spain
Tile	"1412"	"0715"	"1305"	"1609"	"1012"	"0904"	"1602"
.	"1413"	"0716"	"1306"	"1610"	"1013"	"1003"	"1702"
.	"1510"	"0814"	"1307"	"1611"	"1014"	"1004"	"1703"
.	"1511"	"0815"	"1308"	"1612"	"1015"	"1103"	"1704"
	"1512"	"0816"	"1404"	"1709"	"1112"	"1104"	"1705"
	"1513"		"1405"	"1710"	"1113"		"1802"
			"1406"	"1711"	"1114"		"1803"
			"1407"	"1712"	"1115"		"1804"
			"1408"	"1809"	"1212"		"1805"
			"1409"	"1810"	"1213"		"1806"
			"1505"	"1811"	"1214"		"1807"
			"1506"	"1812"	"1215"		"1902"
			"1507"	"1813"	"1312"		"1903"
			"1508"	"1909"	"1313"		"1904"
			"1509"	"1910"	"1314"		"1905"
			"1605"	"1911"	"1315"		"1906"
			"1606"	"1912"	"1414"		"1907"
			"1607"	"1913"	"1415"		"2002"
			"1608"	"1914"			"2003"
			"1609"	"2009"			"2004"
			"1705"	"2010"			"2005"
			"1706"	"2013"			"2006"
			"1707"	"2014"			"2007"
			"1708"	"2111"			"2102"
			"1709"	"2112"			"2103"
			"1806"	"2113"			"2104"
			"1807"	"2211"			"2105"
			"1808"	"2213"			
			"1809"				
			"1810"				
			"1910"				

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Figure D.2.3.2.49: EU-2018-crop reclassified for areas growing wheat (in yellow).

Figure D.2.3.2.50: EU-2018-crop reclassified for areas growing wheat plus the Emilia-Romagna plainland border.

First, each EU-2018-crop tile that is part of the AOI is transformed into a logical raster with the raster calculator. In this case, the input layer is the EU-2018-crop tile, and the value selected is set to 1 (and thus wheat locations are set to 1 and other locations to zero, Figure D.2.3.2.51). Note that this operation had been done before (Figure D.2.3.2.39).

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Figure D.2.3.2.51: Transforming an EU-2018-crop tiles into a logical raster with the raster calculator.

Then, we need to reclassify each logical EU-2018-crop tile for our AOI with the **r.null** operation so that the zero value is set to NULL (Figure D.2.3.2.52). Thus, the locations with wheat are set to 1, and all the other locations to NULL. Again, the NULL reclassification has been done before too (Figure D.2.3.2.44-D.2.3.2.45).

Figure D.2.3.2.52: Setting the logical EU-2018-crop tile value of zero to NULL.

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Now, each EU-2018-crop raster with NULLS needs to be vectorised. The election of algorithm for the vectorisation is important as it determines the processing time. The gdal algorithm present in QGIS (gdal_polygonize, Figure D.2.3.2.53) is rather slow and it might crash with big files.

Figure D.2.3.2.53: Gdal polygonisation algorithm option in the raster menu of QGIS. This algorithm performance might be poor for large raster objects as those from the EU-2018-crop layer.

On the other hand, the GRASS r.to.vect (Figure D.2.3.2.54) performance is superior, so this is the recommended algorithm for vectorisation. Type r.to.vect in the processing search bar to find it and double click it.

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Figure D.2.3.2.54: *r.to.vect* algorithm option in the processing search bar of QGIS.

Fill in the needed parameters for the vectorisation of the raster EU-2018-crop tiles (Figures D.2.3.2.55-Figure D.2.3.2.56), mainly: the input raster (that coming from the *r.null* reclassification, Figure D.2.3.2.52), the type of attribute (set to area), and the name of the attribute column to be created (this column name should be the same for each EU-2018-crop tile of your AOI to be vectorised). If you are vectorising one tile at a time (vs doing several raster tiles at once in batch mode), you might set the output vector to a temporary file (Figure D.2.3.2.56). This is because the output vector layer still must be reprojected (the reprojection step can be done when saving the temporary vector layer into a permanent file). Vectorising of each raster tile takes around 5-7 minutes on a standard system.

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Figure D.2.3.2.55: r.to.vect options to be filled in to vectorise the EU-2018-crop raster tiles.

Figure D.2.3.2.56: r.to.vect option to save the vectorized layer to a temporary file.

The reprojection of each vector layer of the EU-2018-crop tiles can be done simply when saving the temporary vector file. This is done by first clicking the mouse's right-button when the layer to be saved is selected and selecting "Save As" in the Export option. (Figure D.2.3.2.57).

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Figure D.2.3.2.57: Saving the vectorised layer from a temporary to a permanent file.

In the pop-up window to save the vectorised raster, we need to fill in the permanent file name, the layer name (the vector layer, usually the same as the vector file name), and, importantly, to set the CRS to that we defined in step 4 (Figure D.2.3.2.58).

Figure D.2.3.2.58: Information to be filled in for saving the vector created from the EU-2018-crop raster tile.

Once all the EU-2018-crop tiles have been converted to logic rasters, then reclassified through r.null, vectorised, and then reprojected, the resulting vector files can be merged into a single one. This is

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done by searching in the QGIS processing search bar for "merge vector", selecting the option, and filling in the needed values to complete the operation (Figures D.2.3.2.59-D.2.3.2.61). For this Emilia-Romagna example, merging 3 vector files resulted in merged file of around 850 Mb. Take note that the operation might last a while depending on your system and the number of vector tiles to be merged.

Figure D.2.3.2.59: Merge vector layers operation in QGIS.

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Figure D.2.3.2.60: Merge vector layers options to be filled in.

Figure D.2.3.2.61: Option in the vector layers operation window where the layers to be merged are selected.

A couple of additional operations are needed to make the zonal statistic process more efficient. First, the resulting merged vector layer geometries need to be fixed. To fix the geometries type **Fix geometries** in the search bar of the processing tool in QGIS (Figure D.2.3.2.62), and enter the arguments needed and save the fix geometry to your pre-established outputs folder (Figure D.2.3.2.63).

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Figure D.2.3.2.62: Fixing geometries of the EU-2018-crop vector layer merged.

Figure D.2.3.2.63: Fixing geometries of the EU-2018-crop merged vector layer selecting input, and determining output.

At this stage, the resulting merged vector layer with fixed geometries could be cut down with the AOI border (in vector format and at the same CRS projection as the other spatial data) to speed up the zonal statistics process. This operation might take a while depending on your system, and the sizes of

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the merged EU-2018-crop vector layers and the AOI. For cutting down the merged layer with the AOI one only goes to the **Clip** option of the **Vector** menu (Figure D.2.3.2.64) and fills in the argument needed to clip the merged EU 2018 crop map layer with the political borders of the AOI (Figure D.2.3.2.65). The result of the vector clipping can be seen in Figure D.2.3.2.66.

Figure D.2.3.2.64: Selecting the clip vector layer option from the main menu.

Figure D.2.3.2.65: Arguments needed to clip the EU-2018-crop merged vector layer with fix geometries with the AOI border.

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Figure D.2.3.2.66: The EU-2018-crop layer (with fixed geometries) clipped for the Emilia-Romagna Region.

The resulting clipped vector layer is made up of polygons of land that correspond to wheat fields within the AOI. The last step is to transfer the values of the NEP filtered indicator produced in step 11 to these layer polygons. If you do the zonal statistics without clipping the merged vector layer, this will take longer. To do so type zonal statistics in the QGIS processing search bar and click on it (Figure D.2.3.2.67).

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Figure D.2.3.2.67: Selecting zonal statistics to transfer the raster NEP values generated in step 11 to the clipped layer having wheat field polygons.

In the pop-up window (Figure D.2.3.2.68), we need to fill in the required arguments: (1) the input vector layer to which the values will be transferred (this is the clipped EU-2018-crop layer), (2) the raster with the NEP values (created in step 11), (3) the name of the prefix to be added to the attribute columns' names , (4) the path and name of the output vector, and (5) the statistic(s) to be calculated with the zonal statistics, at least the **mean** should be selected, but other possibilities include the median and the standard deviation (Figure D.2.3.2.69). Once this is completed, we can run the process.

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Figure D.2.3.2.68: Zonal statistics arguments to transfer the raster NEP values generated in step 11 to the clipped layer with wheat field polygons.

Figure D.2.3.2.69: Selection of the statistic(s) to be used in to transfer NEP values to the polygons of the EU –2018-crop clipped layer. In this case they are the mean, the median, and the standard deviation.

Finally, we have our spatialised indicator of filtered NEP values (Figure D.2.3.2.70). Again, this should ideally be done for the whole year 2014 in order to look for some 8-d periods that can be representative of the annual variation for the indicator.

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Figure D.2.3.2.70: The final NEP indicator for the Emilia-Romagna region for the first 8-d of the 2014 year. NEP data have been filtered out (spurious values produced for covariates beyond the ranges used to fit the model). They correspond to areas of wheat crops in 2018 (either common or durum wheat). This is for a single 8-d period. Given the limitations in the data input a relatively large section of the coastal area in the East has null values (not shown here).

Details correspond to how to render the vector layer NEP values (number of classes, colours, etc.). As this is considered more ornamental, not much detail will be offered here. For a more extensive treatment of the subject there is widely available material online (both videos and tutorials, such as the one from QGIS: https://docs.qgis.org/3.34/en/docs/training_manual/basic_map/symbology.html).

If you are doing a regional-level or country-level analysis for a relatively small country, you might work in this way. For relatively bigger countries the whole EU 2018 crop tile level might be more efficient, but more computing capacity will be needed. In this case you might clip the annual NEP indicator (filtered for spurious values) with the country’s political borders.

Update

An R script has been available to be able to calculate the annual NEP indicator in a rather quick way for relatively small regions (such as that of ERR). The script can be found here: [Link to Zenodo Repository](#)

The only thing that needs to be changed with respect to the previous cookbook is:

- 1) The World Climate tmax and tmin temperature files need to have a particular structure in their respective folders. This structure aligns the number of monthly files to the MODIS number of products in a month (Figure D.2.3.2.71). In Figure D.2.3.2.71 it can be seen that for maximum temperature each month file has a number of copies as it needs to be used according to the number of MODIS products in Table D.2.3.2.12. For instance, there are 4 8-d

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periods in January so that there are 4 January maximum temperature file copies in the folder. For February this number is 3 and so on. The same needs to be done with minimum temperature.

- 2) The AOI in vector format in both CRS WGS84 and in the CRS of the moisture dataset are needed to crop the rasters (you can reproject a vector file of your AOI in QGIS for this)

With this you can follow the script and skipped steps 1-11, then you recontinue from step 12. Note that the annual indicator of NEP overestimates the fluxes notably.

Figure D.2.3.2.71: Files structure of monthly maximum and minimum temperatures needed to run the R script. Here only maximum monthly temperature is shown.

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5.4.7. Interpretation

NEP is a highly spatio-temporal dynamic variable, with strong seasonal patterns. Given that the indicator was created with high-frequency data (each 8-days or monthly data), at this stage the indicator provides a picture of the controls on NEP determined mainly by climate and seasonal patterns in soil moisture and temperature. This does not mean that soil properties and management aspects are not important (see Zhou et al., 2021), but now they are at this moment only implicitly present based on their effects on soil moisture and the estimate of GPP in the MODIS products used. In order to include soil properties explicitly annual variation in the indicator for the training sites needs to be related to soil properties and other variables of lower spatial resolution at a second stage of the cookbook development.

The next figure shows the conditions (i.e., the combination of values of the input explanatory variables) that determine the value and sign of the modelled NEP; given the models for GPP and RECO used. The red curve shows the behavior of RECO for the range of average monthly temperature values used (x axis) in the fitting of the thermal performance model. On the other hand, the green-gradient areas (contours) show the variation in the values of the modelled GPP for different values of MODIS 8-d GPP (y axis) and average monthly temperature (x axis). Soil moisture values might modify this general pattern (Figure D.2.3.2.73). As can be seen, NEP will be negative in the region under the curve (this is under combination of low values of MODIS and a wide range of temperatures). On the other hand, positive values of NEP will be obtained in general for high values of MODIS GPP under a wide range of temperatures.

Based on the application of the cookbook and subsequent analyses, it is recommended to use at least two 8-d periods for representing the variability of the indicator intra-annually: 1) the period with the highest values (in the case of ERR this was in early summer, see D3.3 application for Italy), and 2) the period with lowest values (in the case of ERR this was in early winter, see D3.3 application for Italy).

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Figure D.2.3.2.72: Contour plot of modelled GPP values (green gradient) under the combination of MODIS 8-d GPP (y axis) and average monthly temperature (x axis), and behavior of RECO with average monthly temperature. The area under the red curve presents negative NEP values, the area above positive ones. The shaded gray area corresponds to conditions when GPP values are negative and as such do not have physical sense.

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Figure D.2.3.2.73: Perspective plot of the joint effects of the combination of MODIS 8-d GPP (x axis) and average soil moisture (y axis) on the resulting GPP predicted values. Note the maximum reduction on predicted GPP caused by soil moisture is around 10 units (more visible in the upper part of the plot).

5.4.8. Further reading

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5.5. Bundles of ST/SES

5.5.1. Selected indicators

The indicators selected in this cookbook are used only for demonstration on how to apply the methods (by trying to create a reproducible example). The method shown requires quantitative variables (SES/ST) that have been previously scaled (min-max) and have the same spatial structure (same spatial resolution and defined at the same grid). In the case of the SES/ST produced by the other cookbooks in the SERENA project, they will need to be resampled and reprojected to same spatial structure (grid, spatial resolution) and coordinated reference system. In some cases some files will have to be transformed to raster (rasterised) to be compatible.

ST/SES	Indicator	units
SOC loss	Carbon eroded	t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
Erosion	Sheet and rill erosion	t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
Primary biomass production	Crop productivity index	Dimensionless

5.5.2. Selected methodology

K-means clustering

Tips and tricks: the Bundles Working Group has developed an R-script (.qmd file) that computes the bundles of the selected indicators.

Elaborated by: E. Medina-Roldán, J. Reyes-Rojas, SERENA Bundles Working Group

5.5.3. Scope/output

Very briefly what the method is about and what is the result. Also what is not included
Bundles have been defined in the frame of the project as “sets of ecosystem services that appear together repeatedly in time and space” (SERENA D2.1). Whereas the term bundle and the range of analytical tools used to delineate them has been traditionally limited to ecosystem services (ES), in this cookbook we will extend the term and analyses to both indicators of soil ES (SES) and to soil threats (ST). In the project we loosely used the term “a posteriori” analysis to indicate that the bundles’ analyses would be focused on SES/ST predetermined by MS’s interest rather than by potential hypothesis testing regarding the drivers that determine such SES/ST bundles. In this way we will describe analysis to delineate bundles of soil threats (ST), soil-based ecosystem services (SES) or the combination of the two. Such analyses of bundles’ detection utilise various statistical methods as no universal method exists. One of the main strategies found in the literature though (accounting for the large majority of papers) is multivariate cluster analyses (k-means or hierarchical clustering, Saidi and Spray (2018)). From this, k-means clustering is the simplest and the most commonly used clustering method for splitting a dataset into a set of k groups.

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K-means is an unsupervised clustering method where the k number of clusters has to be defined in advance (the following discussion follows mainly Legendre and Legendre 2012). K-means clustering partitions a multivariate data space into the pre-defined k clusters, each with a mean value. The points within the same cluster are as similar as possible as the method reduces intra-cluster variability with respect to inter-cluster variability. Each cluster is represented by its centroid which corresponds to the arithmetic means of the different variables forming the multivariate data space in that particular cluster (Sterling et al., 2017). In terms of bundles analysis, this means that bundles are just clusters in which values of SES/SES, SES/ST or SES/ST at a given location are more similar to its own cluster centroid than to other cluster centroids. The values of the clusters centroid (defined by the SES or ST means' vector) are usually depicted in a spiderweb, radar plot or bar plot; and they represent the SES/ST "signatures" of the bundle (Saidi et al., 2018). Several algorithms have been implemented to compute the method, they work through an iterative process until each data point is closer to its own cluster centroid, minimizing intra-cluster variability with respect to inter-cluster variability at each step. According to Sterling et al. (2017) the k-means is computed in the following steps:

The algorithm randomly chooses a centroid for each cluster.

Assignment of every multivariate data point in the dataset to the nearest centroid, meaning that a data point is in a particular cluster if it is closer to that cluster's centroid than any other centroid.

For every cluster, the algorithm recomputes the centroid by taking the average of all points in the cluster reducing the total intra-cluster variance in relation to the previous step.

The algorithm repeats the calculation of centroids and assignment of points until the sum of distances between the data points and their corresponding centroid is minimised, a maximum number of iterations is reached or no changes in the centroid's values are produced.

K-means is scalable to large datasets and has a relatively simple implementation. It also offers computational efficiency when compared to other clustering methods (Mussabayev et al., 2023). K-means clustering has its drawbacks though. One major limitation is the requirement to define the number of clusters in advance (note that inter-cluster variability is reduced as k increases, so in theory one can always choose a $k+1$ number to reduce such variability until $k = N$). The number of clusters chosen can significantly impact the results. Several methods to find an "optimal" value for " k " exist, but they have to be used together with the expertise of the phenomenon in question, as well the interpretability of the final results. A related aspect not well explored in the literature is whether the method should be used as a dimensional reduction technique (i.e., $k < \text{number of SES/ST used in the analysis}$), or should not (Esau et al., 2023). Yet another shortcoming of the technique is that intra-cluster variability of SES/ST values is obscured (in the sense that is not interpreted for the final k -clusters solution).

Here we present the cookbook to analyse SES/SES, ST/ST or SES/ST bundles using k-means. The cookbook is based on an exercise where indicators of organic carbon loss, and soil erosion (ST) together with an indicator of productivity (biomass) for agricultural areas are analysed to produce bundles at the EU scale. However, the cookbook can be applied to other indicators of SES/ST as long as they are:

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- 1) Quantitative
- 2) Spatially-explicit, with same “spatial structure” (this is they are defined at the same grid and with the same spatial resolution or spatial support)
- 3) Min-max-scaled

5.5.4. Data and harmonization

The following table shows the variables used in this cookbook to demonstrate the application of the method.

Data type		Database	Indicator	Unit	Resolution (km)	Projection	Type spatial	Year	Land use	Preprocessing
ST	SOC loss (eroded)	JRC	Eroded soil organic carbon	t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	1	Projection: ETRS_LAEA	raster	2000-2010	Agriculture land	
ST	Soil erosion	JRC	Soil loss by water	t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	0.1	Projection: ETRS_LAEA	raster	2016	Agriculture land	Data gaps filled through an iterative process using an IWD algorithm ∞
SES	Primary biomass production	JRC	Biomass production	Dimensionless (1-10)	1	ETRS_LAEA_10_52	raster	2013	Agriculture land	Data gaps filled through an iterative process using an IWD algorithm ∞
EU extent		EUROSTAT	*	Dimensionless	*	ETRS_LAEA_10_52	vector	2021		

∞See Appendix Bundles I for more details: [Link Zenodo Repository](#)

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5.5.5. Software

R studio/R

5.5.6. Application

Step 1. Data inputs and data preparation

- a. It is needed to create a folder with a meaningful name for the project for input and output information (you might keep input and output folders as separate within a project's folder). In RStudio: File > New Project > Existing Directory > Browse > The folder just created > Select Folder > Create Project, this will result in a file with extension. Rproj, but other settings are possible (for instance people who work in other editors different than RStudio)
- b. Download the raster and vector data, and load them into R; and preprocessing. In our case, these are data layers acquired from ESDAC. To start the analysis we need to have the inputs (spatially-explicit information on SES/ST) ready. In the R code in the Appendix (Bundles Cookbook.pdf), the raster inputs are represented by the variables: (1) "SOC_loss" (from C_eroded_prj.tif), (2) "PBP" (from biomass_filled.tif), and (3) "Erosion" from (erosion_filled.tif). All data has to have the same spatial extent, and to be at the same CRS, grid structure, and spatial resolution. In the case of the example, the CRS and grid correspond to the ETRS89-LAEA grid. Then, the layers are cropped to the same extent by using the political borders of the EU. Additionally, since "Erosion" has a different spatial resolution, this needs to be made comparable to the other variables. This is done with the resampling part of the code.

Step 2. Transform the SES/ST variables to have a similar metric.

The variables need to have a similar numeric range, otherwise those with a higher absolute value will have a higher weight in the analysis. Whereas there is no consensus in the literature on the variable transformation to be performed (e.g., Mouchet et al. 2014, Fig. 2), a number of transformations are among the commonest ones. One of such transformations is carried out with the mix-man scaling of the form $x_i' = (x_i - x_{min}) / (x_{max} - x_{min})$, where x_i' corresponds to a scaled observation, and x_{max} and x_{min} correspond to the maximum and minimum values of the variable in question (Calzolari et al. 2016).

Step 3. Clustering analysis: Determine the number of k clusters to retain.

There is a vast number of metrics used to determine the number of clusters to be used in the final clustering solution (Liu et al. 2010). For reasons of computing efficiency and ease of interpretation, the example in the script uses several indexes embedded in a standard function in the NbClust package in R (Charrad et al. 2014); but using only with a small sub-sample of the dataset. This approach then determines the optimal k-cluster number by vote counting (this is when the highest number of cluster-quality indexes suggest a k value). For large datasets this approach might be computationally prohibitive though, and an approach with a single elbow method might be the only practical option (see script file).

Step 4. Clustering analysis through k-means.

This step used a standard R function in the package ClusterR (Mouselimis et al. 2023) to split the datasets in the k-clusters determined in the previous step.

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Step 5. Mapping (spatial rendering) of the bundle analysis.

In this step, each spatial unit (in this case a pixel with the same spatial structure and resolution as the input rasters data) which has been assigned a cluster identity (from the previous step) is displayed on a bundles map.

5.5.7. Interpretation

Bundles interpretation is challenging, and it requires expert and theoretical knowledge to understand the co-occurrence of each ST/SES in space and time (Mouchet et al. 2014). To help us to do so, the mean values of each SES/ST in the cluster (centroids) are usually used in conjunction with radar plots to determine the variation in SES/ST in each cluster. An additional step involves either the formulation and testing of hypothesis on potential drivers of the bundles (from here the name “a posteriori” approach used internally in SERENA); or for the direct testing of drivers when such drivers are hypothesised from the beginning of the research (from here the name “a priori” approach). Since we will apply the “a posteriori” approach, interpretation on bundles and drivers might require additional accessory information (such as climate and soil types maps). An Appendix is included with some comparisons to see some aspects of interpretation: [Link Zenodo Repository](#)

5.5.8. Further reading

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6. Conclusions

Deliverable 2.3.1 developed the second step of the harmonization of STs and SESs indicators, whereas this deliverable report the results of the third step of the global tiered strategy for harmonisation (Chapter 3 of this deliverable) and the definition of methods for the harmonised assessment of indicators of STs and SESs at the member state (MS) level. Based on importance of the selected STs/SESs within SERENA, on the interest of MS in specific ST/SES, the possibility to evaluate specific ST/SES, and on the availability of expertise and time of the researchers involved in SERENA, only some of them were selected for developing the cookbooks. Particularly, the STs/SESs selected were:

1. Soil erosion (ST) and soil erosion control (SES)
2. SOC loss (ST)
3. Greenhouse gas (GHG) and climate regulation (SES)
4. Soil sealing (ST).

To these was added a bundle of STs/SESs, which is the result of combining and synthesizing some STs and SESs that are in some way related and that share some of the information provided by the individual STs/SESs indicators. The bundle allowed the effectiveness of reporting the status of some STs/SESs using a single indicator.

The different cookbooks provide harmonized approaches/methods for assessing indicators for STs/SESs at national scale with a certain amount of autonomy of choice left to MSs in relation to their availability of data and expertise. Therefore, in developing the different cookbooks, the following requirements or assumptions were established:

1. Selection of at least one method per indicator (e.g. RUSLE for soil erosion). Perhaps 2, if possible.
2. Assuming mapping at national scale
3. Methods should be feasible for MS (data, software, knowledge)
4. Standard format 'recipe', different methods ST/SES
5. Threshold/reference values to evaluate.

The development of cookbooks for each indicator of ST/SES (including bundles of STs/SESs) reported in this deliverable was only one part of a broader activity that involved several WPs of SERENA with the subsequent application of the cookbooks at MS scale within Task 3.2 (Hessel et al., 2024) and the validation of the results of this application within Task 1.3.

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